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A Practical CFD Philosophy for Computing
Liquid-Induced Energy Dissipation and Pressure
Distributions for Aircraft Design

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Quote

“The universe is, instant by instant, recreated anew. There is in truth no past, only a memory of the past. Blink your eyes, and the world you see next did not exist when you closed them. Therefore, the only appropriate state of the mind is surprise. The only appropriate state of the heart is joy. The sky you see now, you have never seen before. The perfect moment is now. Be glad of it.”

~ Terry Pratchett

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Abstract

The drive for a more environmentally sustainable aviation industry has led to the requirement for improved aircraft structural weight optimisation. A limiting factor in achieving this is the current over-conservatism in estimating slosh-induced energy dissipation and pressure distributions. The over-conservatism is due to the vast range of operational conditions to be considered during design, while very few viable loads estimation techniques are available. This thesis addresses the latter via a novel yet practical CFD-based loads estimation philosophy. This work will be limited to vertical slosh excitations.

To this end, this work will employ experimentally validated CFD as an ideally suited and versatile tool to characterise liquid slosh-induced loads and energy dissipation. It is thus first demonstrated that a FVM-VOF based CFD scheme employing a weakly-compressible gas formulation is capable of computing violent slosh-induced energy dissipation with high accuracy (a 98% correlation with experimental data is achieved). By employing non-dimensional analysis, a functional relationship characterising slosh-induced energy dissipation is formulated in terms of fluid physics-based non-dimensional numbers. Accurate CFD analyses are consequently employed to develop novel scaling laws (curve fits) that quantify energy dissipation as a function of selected fluid physics non-dimensional numbers and geometric scaling. The practical use of the developed scaling laws is next demonstrated by quantifying slosh loads for perfect Froude scaled experiments (with exact fluid physics similarity to the full-scale aircraft) and full-scale systems (practical and achievable Froude scaled experiments) from slosh experiments to an accuracy of 91% and 87% respectively.

The CFD-derived energy dissipation scaling-laws may now be employed within the industry standard full aircraft model (FAM), which employs proprietary ROMs for the structure, aerodynamics and slosh loads. This yields improved global slosh loads but still provides very limited information regarding tank-wall pressure distributions, which negates structural component optimisation. This is addressed via a CFD-based coarse mesh ROM which is non-linear and mass and momentum conservative. The novel Pressure Distribution ROM involves a coarse mesh CFD which is tuned to match input target loads via the automated adjustment of liquid properties, which constitutes the final contribution of this work. It is demonstrated that the new Pressure ROM is capable of computing tank wall pressures and slosh-induced damping to engineering precision while being significantly faster to run as compared to detailed CFD.

Keywords: Full Aircraft Model (FAM); Multi-phase Flows; Non-dimensional Analysis; Violent Slosh-induced Energy Dissipation; Volume of Fluid (VOF) method; Finite

Volume Method (FVM); Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD); Reduced-order Model (ROM).

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

ACFS	Artificial Compressibility Free Surface Method
AGI	Arbitrary Grid Initialiser
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CSM	Computational Solid Mechanics
DAF	Dynamic amplification factor
EASA	European Aviation Safety Agency
FAA	Federal Aviation Authority
FAM	Full Aircraft Model
FMM	Frozen Mass Model
FFT	Flutter Flight Tests
FSI	Fluid-structure Interaction
FSM	Free-surface modelling
FVM	Finite Volume Method
GVT	Ground Vibration Tests
HF	High-fidelity
H2020	European Union Horizon 2020 Projects
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
LES	Large-eddy turbulence simulation method
RMS	Root mean square

ROM	Reduced-order Model
SDOF	Single degree-of-freedom
SLOWD	Sloshing Wing Dynamics
SPH	Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics
UT	Untailored Simulation
VOF	Volume of Fluids

Operators

β	Opimisation cost factor for ideal cpu cost calculation
$\Delta()$	The difference between two states of the same system
$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}$	The Eulerian derivative for the parameter t
$\frac{D}{Dt}$	The material derivative for the parameter t
$\frac{d}{dt}$	The derivative for the parameter t
∇	The gradient operator
$\phi_0 \otimes \phi_1$	The dyadic product of ϕ_0 and ϕ_1
\sum	The sum across indices
$ \phi $	Normalised value of ϕ
$ \phi _2$	Euclidean/ L_2 norm of the vector ϕ
$\bar{\phi}$	Averaged property of ϕ
$R(\phi)$	Range of influence for ϕ
$IQR(\phi)$	Inter Quartile Range of influence for ϕ

Sub- and superscripts

$\bar{\phi}$	time-averaged value of ϕ
ϕ_g	ϕ within the gas phase
ϕ_l	ϕ within the liquid phase
ϕ_i	ϕ at the node i
ϕ_f	ϕ at the mesh face for node i
ϕ_{fs}	ϕ of full-scale system

ϕ^n	Magnitude of ϕ at time step n
$\phi_0\phi_1 ^n$	Magnitudes of ϕ_0 and ϕ_1 at time step n
ϕ_x	Magnitude of ϕ in the x direction
ϕ_y	Magnitude of ϕ in the y direction
ϕ_z	Magnitude of ϕ in the z direction
$\vec{r}_{b/A}$	Vector r to point b with respect to A .

Symbols

α	The volume fraction field	
\mathbf{a}	Acceleration vector	$m.s^{-2}$
A	Atwood number dimensionless quantity	
\tilde{A}	Tank aspect ratio	
c_g	Acoustic velocity of fluid	$m.s^{-1}$
c	Structural Damping	$N.s.m^{-1}$
Δt	Time step size for simulation	s
Δx	Mesh spacing for cartesian mesh	m
$\ \Delta E_{Disp}\ (\phi)$	Variation from the experimental case as a function of ϕ	%
\hat{e}	Unit vector	
η_0	Height of fluid	m
E_{Disp}	Dissipated energy	W
E_{Defo}	Deformation work	W
E_k	Kinetic energy	W
E_M	Mechanical energy	W
E_{ST}	Surface tension energy	W
E_u	Potential energy	W
E_{visc}	Viscous dissipation energy	W
ϵ_p	Error for values of p	
ε	Kinetic energy dissipation rate per a unit mass	

f	Frequency of a system	Hz
\tilde{F}	Liquid fill ratio	
\mathbf{F}	Slosh force vector	N
Fr	Froude number dimensionless quantity	
g	Gravitational constant	$9.81m.s^{-2}$
γ	Fluid surface tension coefficient	$N.m^{-1}$
\mathbb{I}	Identity matrix	
k	Structural Stiffness	$N.m^{-1}$
k_{Turb}	Turbulent kinetic energy per a unit mass	
κ	Interface curvature	$rad.m^{-1}$
λ	Geometric scaling factor	
λ_{LES}	Taylor micro-scale	
μ	Fluid viscosity	$Pa.s$
n	Oscillation count	
N_n	Number of nodes within a FVM mesh	
N_{proc}	Number of processors employed for simulation	
ν	Fluid kinematic viscosity	$Pa.s$
ω	Angular frequency of a system	$rad.s^{-1}$
Ω	Speed up factor for ROM against high-fidelity simulation	
$\boldsymbol{\omega}$	Angular velocity of a system	$rad.s^{-1}$
$\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}$	Angular acceleration of a system	$rad.s^{-2}$
p	Pressure	Pa
Π	Dimensionless group	
Re	Reynold number dimensionless quantity	
ρ	Fluid density	$kg.m^{-3}$
$\bar{\rho}$	Density ratio between gas and liquid	
\mathcal{A}	Control surface surrounding a control volume	m^2

t_{sim}	Total time of simulation	s
t_{CPU}	Real CPU cost for simulation	s
t_{total}	CPU wall time cost for simulation	s
t_{CPU}^*	Ideal CPU cost for simulation	s
θ	Liquid–solid Contact Angle	rad
\mathcal{V}	Control volume	m^3
We	Weber number dimensionless quantity	
W_s	Domain boundary surfaces or surface work	W
Δx	Cartesian mesh spacing	mm
ξ	Damping co-efficient of a system	
ξ_d	Structural damping coefficient	
$\Delta\xi_s$	Slosh-induced damping coefficient	
$y(t)$	Vertical displacement history of a system	m
$\ddot{y}(t)$	Vertical acceleration history of a system	$m.s^{-2}$
\tilde{Y}_0	Dimensionless initial deflection of the mass-spring system	

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

The success and safety of the Aviation Industry occur as a result of the stringent process required by Aviation Certification Agencies in certifying an aircraft, the two largest agencies being the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) and the Federal Aviation Authority (FAA) [1]. The strict enforcement of and close adherence to regulations by regulators and manufacturers respectively during the design, manufacture, servicing and decommissioning of aircraft has allowed air transport to become one of the safest modes of travel with a fatality statistic approximately 50,000 times safer than that for motor vehicles [1]. Recent demands on the industry as a result of public perception and climate change have led to campaigns to ensure a safer, more reliable and environmentally sustainable aviation industry [2].

Established in 1970, Airbus is the world's largest passenger aircraft manufacturer with approximately 56% of all current commercial aircraft orders worldwide [3]. Airbus is a manufacturer with a commitment to the production of innovative commercial aircraft that leverage continuous innovation and technology to develop sustainable safe, lighter and more fuel-efficient aircraft [4] to achieve the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) goal of carbon-neutral growth in the aviation industry by 2020 and net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 [5].

The certification process as drafted by the EASA requires the design and modelling of an aircraft over the full flight envelope. This includes various combinations of altitudes, flight velocities and loading conditions [6] and can be represented as a pair of acceleration-frequency maps, as presented in Figure 1.1. To certify an aircraft requires millions of simulations of the aircraft over its full operational envelope. For this purpose, a full aircraft model (FAM) is required which models and accounts for external aerodynamic

flow, structural behaviour and responses, and internal fuel slosh loads all operating as a coupled fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulation [7].

(a)

(b)

Figure 1.1: Acceleration-frequency map for aircraft certification [8] (a) Lateral acceleration; (b) Vertical acceleration

Completing such certification utilising high-fidelity simulations, which makes use of both computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and computational solid mechanics (CSM) and is, as such, prohibitively costly in computational time as it requires hundreds of thousands of cases to be run. As a result, reduced-order models (ROMs) are employed to capture the global physics at reduced computational costs while maintaining the level of accuracy required by EASA regulations to identify and select critical design cases [9]. ROMs provide a mathematical representation of the dominant physics and provide an approximate reproduction of the full-order dynamic system [10]. Significant progress has

Figure 1.2: Airbus condensed point load structural ROM

been made in the accuracy of the structural [11, 12] and aerodynamic [13, 14] ROMs. The current FAM slosh ROM has two components: the slosh loads model and slosh pressure model. These provide the slosh load and tank pressure distributions in computationally efficient manner while remaining consistent with the EASA regulations [15]. The slosh loads are calculated by means of a so-called frozen mass model (FMM), which models the fluid as an equally distributed mass undergoing an excitation. Therefore, the slosh loads are calculated as

$$\mathbf{F}_{slosh} = m_l \mathbf{a}_{tank} \quad (1.1)$$

where m_l and \mathbf{a}_{tank} are respectively the liquid mass and tank acceleration.

The secondary component is a quasi-static pressure model. This model is utilised to provide an estimation of the tank static pressure distributions due to an excitation. The model assumes a quasi-static perfectly flat liquid surface, which is normal to the resultant tank acceleration, where the resulting static pressure head provides the tank pressure distribution.

Due to the reduced complexity of the above slosh ROM, it does not allow for specific fuel tank component optimisation as it is unable to provide realistic dynamic pressure distributions within the tank. Though being computationally fast, the current slosh ROM has several shortcomings [16] which prohibit a new level of aircraft structural weight optimisation:

- It does not account for the added dynamic energy dissipation due to fuel slosh.

This would improve structural fatigue life calculations of wings which are constantly being excited in flight.

- The liquid distribution (centre of gravity) due to wing dynamic tank motion is not provided. This affects handling qualities and as a result complex internal systems are added to wing tanks to compartmentalise the tanks dynamically.
- A simplified estimate of the total force due to fuel slosh on the wing structure wall is provided.
- Pressure loadings due to fluid impact within the tank are omitted.

The need to address these shortcomings is particularly valuable when considering that jet fuel accounts for about 30% of a large passenger aircraft's weight at take-off, all of which is contained in the wings in single-aisle passenger aircraft such as the A320. This weight and resulting loads are considerable, and have significant effects on not only the aerodynamic stability and aircraft control characteristics during flight and ground manoeuvres, [17] but also structural fatigue life estimates.

The influence of liquid centre of mass motion (due to slosh) has been acknowledged by the industry as a result of the clear changes to the aircraft flutter boundaries at various tank fill-level configurations [18]. To account for the change in frequencies due to fuel mass, ground vibration tests (GVT) are performed. To obtain very limited slosh-induced energy dissipation estimates, Flutter Flight Tests (FFT) are employed. Both of the aforementioned tests are, however, typically done on the full-scale aircraft prototype [17] and are thus subsequent to the main design phase.

Past work to incorporate damping within the aircraft design process has included aeroelastic studies [18] with a focus on general trends and changes in flutter boundaries, and the implementation of tuned liquid dampers within the system [19, 20]. These campaigns neglected the vertical motion of the tank, employing seismic shaking tables to provide the excitation to the structure.

An alternative is the use of small-scale experimental campaigns to allow for the extrapolation (through non-dimensional analysis) of the expected slosh-induced energy damping and slosh loads expected for the full-sized system. An example of such an experimental campaign is the Protospace Experimental campaign [21, 22] (section 2.3.1) which attempted to provide a one-fifth scaled slosh model of a single-aisle aircraft wing. However, due to limitations in budget, material and fluid availabilities, these small-scale experimental campaigns do not allow for ideal scaling of all non-dimensional quantities (ensuring similar fluid Reynolds number, Froude number, etc.) and operate at limited discrete points on

the acceleration-frequency map. Due to these limitations, this approach is not currently widely employed as a standard industrial approach. This thesis will seek to address this by complementing the scale experiments with CFD-generated non-dimensional scaling curves. These scaling curves are proposed to span the full aircraft operational range.

Figure 1.3: Current industrial global slosh and pressure loads philosophy

Figure 1.3 depicts the current standard industrial methodology to provide, as alluded to previously, the global slosh and pressure loads. The structural and aerodynamic ROMs within the FAM are tailored to account for changes in wing natural frequency and slosh-induced dissipation. The tailoring of parameters is informed by the FFT and GVT experimental campaigns conducted on the aircraft prototype.

To address the above weaknesses in industrial practices, and include violent slosh loads and energy dissipation in the main aircraft design phase, the EU Horizon 2020 project SLOWD (SLOshing Wing Dynamics) [17] aims to characterise and model the impact of fuel loads and sloshing on the damping characteristics of a wing structure – with particular focus on vertical excitation where the direction of excitation is normal to the liquid free-surface. As part of the SLOWD project, this thesis therefore aims to develop industrially applicable high- and low-fidelity slosh models capable of accurately

modelling both the slosh loads and slosh-induced energy dissipation for such cases.

1.2 Objectives and Scope

As part of the SLOWD project, this thesis intends to propose a novel, yet practical, CFD-based loads estimation philosophy to improve on the existing FAM loads estimation procedure for modelling slosh-induced energy dissipation and transient pressure distributions for vertical slosh excitations. The initial FAM loads estimation procedure, as depicted in Figure 1.3, employs simplified methods for the estimation of slosh pressure distributions while system energy dissipation is almost completely neglected. The latter is addressed in some form only after tuning via GVT campaigns [23].

Figure 1.4: Proposed improved global slosh and pressure loads philosophy

As such, Figure 1.4 provides an overview of the proposed improved philosophy where the novel contributions of this thesis are marked in red. The proposed philosophy employs non-dimensional techniques to predict a reasonable slosh-induced energy dissipation across the full range of operational conditions. To complement the new spring mass type slosh ROM being developed by the other partners in SLOWD project, this work enables the replacement of the quasi-static frozen mass model with a non-linear CFD-based ROM to provide accurate dynamic pressure distributions on the tank walls. This would allow improved global slosh loads by means of a novel mechanical slosh model.

Employing non-dimensional analysis, a functional relationship characterising slosh-induced energy dissipation is formulated in terms of fluid physics-based non-dimensional numbers. Accurate CFD analyses are consequently employed to develop novel scaling laws (curve fits) that quantify slosh load and energy dissipation as a function of selected fluid physics non-dimensional numbers and geometric scaling. These scaling laws are then employed within the FAM loads estimation procedure to provide increased realism in the initial FAM response by incorporating the fluid damping.

A new improved spring mass slosh ROM is being developed as part of SLOWD. It aims to produce more accurate global slosh loads due to wing excitation (as compared to FMM), but does not offer information relating to liquid interface position and thus tank pressure distributions. To address this, the final contribution of this thesis entails the development of a non-linear, mass and momentum conservative fuel slosh ROM which provides approximate interface positions and tank wall pressure distributions to allow for structural component optimisation. This ROM is developed to operate with an arbitrary tank and liquid fill level utilising the global slosh loads and tank kinetics (excitation history).

Note that to limit the scope of work, this thesis will consider only vertical slosh and a tank fill level of 50% as a representative case for the evaluation (50% was found to offer significant slosh damping for both the full Protospace and single compartment experimental campaigns [21, 24, 25]). Additionally, the of an intermediate tank depth, leads to the exclusion of the the two limit states of shallow or very deep tanks.

To further limit the scope of the work, the influence of the liquid fill level related non-dimensional number was kept constant throughout (see Eq. 2.8), by means of ensuring tank height and displacement amplitude is constant by means of varying acceleration amplitude due to frequency change. And thus, it is recommended that further work should be considered to include this non-dimensional number.

1.3 Original Contributions in the Work

This work presents several novel contributions:

- A CFD-based non-dimensional characterisation of violent slosh-induced global loads and energy dissipation is due to a tank under vertical excitation. Experimentally validated CFD is used for this purpose as an ideally suited and versatile tool. It is thus first demonstrated that a finite volume method (FVM) CFD scheme employing a volume of fluid (VOF) technique and weakly-compressible gas formulation is capable of computing violent slosh loads and induced energy dissipation with high accuracy.
- A functional relationship characterising slosh-induced energy dissipation is formulated in terms of fluid physics-based non-dimensional numbers. These comprised contact angle and liquid–gas density ratio as well as Reynolds, Weber and Froude numbers. These scaling laws are then employed to infer slosh-induced energy dissipation for ideal experiments (with exact fluid physics similarity to the full-scale Aircraft) in addition to informing frequency-based slosh dissipation for the FAM.
- The development of a non-linear, mass and momentum conservative FVM-VOF based prototype reduced-order model providing the slosh-induced dynamic pressure distributions on the tank walls. The prototype ROM should employ the tank geometry, liquid fill-level, tank excitation and target global loads (as computed via the FAM or experimental measurements) as inputs. This ROM should offer significant cost savings as compared to conventional high resolution CFD (as employed previously).

1.4 Plan of Development

This work is organised as follows.

- **Chapter 2:** Key information pertaining to the Protospace experimental campaign is presented, given that it forms the base from which this study operates. The chapter concludes with the presentation of the relevant experiential results from the campaign.
- **Chapter 3:** The mathematical formulation for the governing equations employed for the modelling of weakly compressible, isothermal two-phase flow is presented. A comprehensive energy budget for the total mechanical energy of the sloshing system

is then described. This energy budget is employed to estimate slosh-induced energy dissipation and evaluated through both two- and three-dimensional simulations.

- **Chapter 4:** The derivation of the excitation profile employed for the high-fidelity CFD simulations from the Protospace experimental campaign is presented. Following this, the multi-physics FVM-VOF code ELEMENTAL[®] [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 8, 31, 32] is validated against experimental results utilising both 2D and 3D simulations.
- **Chapter 5:** A non-dimensional analysis of violent vertical slosh is outlined and the sensitivity studies on the effects of identified non-dimensional numbers within a selected parameter space are quantified.
- **Chapter 6:** Functional relationships characterising slosh-induced energy dissipation are derived and evaluated for the non-geometrical scaling. The scaling law for the geometric scaling of violent sloshing systems is derived. Finally, scaling laws are then assessed against high-fidelity CFD simulations and their accuracy is evaluated.
- **Chapter 7:** The proposed slosh pressure distribution ROM is described. Following this, the novel operational algorithm of the proposed non-linear FVM reduced-order pressure distribution model is detailed.
- **Chapter 8:** The numerical test-cases are tabled for the proposed FVM reduced-order pressure distribution model, which is then evaluated.
- **Chapter 9:** The conclusions and recommendations of this work are presented.

Chapter 2

Protospace Experimental Campaign

2.1 Introduction

Structural damping due to violent vertical slosh is a new topic, particularly with regard to quantifying its effect on structural vibration. For this reason, Airbus commissioned the so-called Protospace experimental campaign in 2018 [21]. The objective of this campaign was the initial quantification of vertical slosh-induced damping for aircraft wing-based fuel tanks. It thus consisted of a scale model of an aircraft wing. This forms part of the design philosophy which leverages lab-scaled experiential campaigns as a method of providing insight into both the slosh-induced dissipation and fluid response to excitation. Therefore, this chapter aims at providing a brief overview of the industrially employed scaling techniques employed. Following this, a summary of the Protospace experimental campaign is presented, including the relevant findings from the experimental campaign. The chapter concludes with the presentation of a simplified single-degree-of-freedom test case to be employed within this thesis as a representative case for the novel CFD-based scaling law work.

2.2 Scaling of Violent Sloshing Systems

To provide a perfect scaled experiment requires complete mechanical similarity with the full-scale system. This implies geometric, kinetic and dynamic similarity (identical force ratios for all terms within the fluid momentum conservation equation - see Equation 3.17). While it is possible to achieve geometric and kinetic similarity, ensuring complete dynamic similarity is not practically feasible. Such scaling requires identical non-dimensional numbers for all flow physics related ratios ($\bar{\rho}$, Re etc.), which is impossible using available fluids. As a result, the experimental similarity of the most important

non-dimensional number is then targeted in industry, which in the case of slosh-induced loads is the Froude number. Note that when designing the Protospace experiment, the non-dimensional number which is key to slosh-induced energy dissipation was uncertain.

2.2.1 Froude Scaling Rules

For experimental scale, it is possible to achieve consistent (ideal) geometric scaling $\lambda = h/h_{fs}$, where h_{fs} is the tank height at full scale, such that this scaling factor applies to all the geometric ratios. As noted above, slosh fluid physics is then commonly scaled using the Froude number. In the case of vibration-induced vertical slosh this is defined as:

$$Fr = \omega_{fs} \sqrt{\frac{h_{fs}}{g}} = \omega \sqrt{\frac{h}{g}} \quad (2.1)$$

where ω and h are respectively the experimental tank excitation frequency and tank height. Further, g is gravitational acceleration. From (2.1) it follows that

$$\frac{\omega}{\omega_{fs}} = \sqrt{\frac{h_{fs}}{h}} = \lambda^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.2)$$

Consequently, the Froude scaling for time t is

$$\frac{t}{t_{fs}} = \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.3)$$

Ensuring Froude similarity constrains two of the three fundamental units: length and time. The rule for mass is generally achieved by simply using a test fluid of the same density as the full-scale (in fact, when possible, the same fluid is used). This assumption leads to

$$\frac{m}{m_{fs}} = \frac{\rho h^3}{\rho_{fs} h_{fs}^3} = \lambda^3 \quad (2.4)$$

Table 2.1 presents some of the remaining scaling rules that follow from those derived above for length, time and mass.

Table 2.1: Froude scaling rules

Quantity		Units			Factor
		M	L	T	
Length	$[m]$	0	1	0	λ
Time	$[s]$	0	0	1	$\lambda^{1/2}$
Mass	$[kg]$	1	0	0	λ^3
Velocity	$[m.s^{-1}]$	0	1	-1	$\lambda^{1/2}$
Acceleration	$[m.s^{-2}]$	0	1	-2	$\lambda^0 = 1$
Viscosity	$[Pa.s]$	1	-1	-1	$\lambda^{1.5}$
Surface tension	$[N.m^{-1}]$	1	0	-2	λ^2
Force	$[N]$	1	1	-2	λ^3
Energy	$[J]$	1	2	-2	λ^4
Power	$[W]$	1	1	-1	$\lambda^{3.5}$

2.3 Protospace Experimental Campaign

2.3.1 Protospace Experiment Introduction

Figure 2.1: Protospace experimental beam design

The Protospace experimental campaign [21, 22] as conducted by Gamioli and Usach was designed to provide a one-fifth scale Froude-scaled representation of a wing-fuel tank for a single-aisle commercial passenger aircraft. The campaign provided a preliminary investigation into sloshing-related damping in aircraft wings, which then served as the basis for the H2020 SLOWD Project. Instrumentation of both the tank and the beam allowed an analysis of the fluid force response and dissipative effects of liquid sloshing. The objective of the campaign was to prove the significance of violent vertical slosh on

the free vibration of a cantilever beam (Figure 2.1) as a result of fuel sloshing. The experiment involved applying an initial deflection (Figure 2.2a) and then releasing a cantilever at $t = 0s$, followed by free vibration and resulting liquid slosh (Figure 2.2b) [22]. This resulted in a maximum acceleration of $10g$ at the beam-tip, which is similar to what single-aisle commercial passenger aircraft wings undergo as a result of gust loading.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.2: Protospace experimental captures (a) Initial negative deflection of beam; (b) Maximum positive deflection of beam

2.3.2 Protospace Experimental Setup

The Protospace experimental setup aimed to provide a scaled representation of a single-aisle commercial passenger aircraft wing and the corresponding wing-tank, such that the following parameters were kept constant: the ratio between tank span and height, the ratio between liquid and structural mass (for a 50% liquid fill level) and the ratio between tank and beam length, maintaining the correct scaling for the first bending frequency. A 2.35m span H-section steel cantilever beam and a tank mounted at the beam tip were utilised, providing a reasonable representation of the wing.

However, as shown in Table 2.2, the Protospace experiment did not achieve the required Fr number. With the available materials, it was not possible to reach a closer similarity, as this would have required a bespoke cantilever design. The lower natural frequency of 3.35 Hz would have implied a greater initial displacement of the free-end, possibly leading to a geometrically non-linear oscillation of the beam. Furthermore, the fact that the resulting characteristic velocity achieved is higher than that required by Fr similarity could indicate that the dissipative effects due to liquid impact are overestimated experimentally if compared to an ideally Froude-scaled experiment. Work has been completed as part of the SLOWD project to attempt to quantify the effects of such practical scaling. This includes experimental campaigns such as [24].

Within the SLOWD project work experimental,

Table 2.2: Froude parameters for Protospace Experimental Campaign

	f [Hz]	Fr
Ideal Experiment	3.35	2.81
Protospace	7.25	5.86

Despite this overestimation, the campaign allowed the investigation of the damping within wing-fluid structures specifically where the dominant acceleration vector acts perpendicular to the free surface and the periodic nature of the excitation results in multiple fluid-structure impacts.

The tank was designed to provide seven sealed compartments with the following dimensions: $0.1m \times 0.06m \times 0.11m$. Sealed compartments were selected to limit the formation of fluid jet-flow through baffles and therefore allowed for representing the experiment by a single compartment for the purpose of subsequent CFD-based investigations. The tank was designed and fitted to limit the transfer of longitudinal forces during the beam oscillation (which would effect the dynamic of the beam) and provide a horizontal tank

when the beam is held at its initial deflection before release. Additionally, the design allowed for the addition of dry mass, directly below the centre of mass of the tank. The addition of ballast allowed the experiment to maintain a constant beam fundamental bending mode. Therefore, three unique beam and tank configurations were achieved, namely: standard (beam and tank fitment with no additional masses or liquid), dry mass (beam and tank with ballast addition to provide $6.5kg$ of weight) and wetted mass (beam and tank with a specified fuel fill level, and additional ballast added such that the fuel mass and ballast comes to $6.5kg$).

Table 2.3: Table comparing key parameters for Protospace experiment and aircraft wing

Parameter	Aircraft	Ideal Froude- scaled	Protospace
Maximum Vertical Acceleration	$\approx 13g$	$\approx 13g$	$\approx 11g$
Tank span to height	≈ 11.67	11.67	11.67
Wingspan to tank span	≈ 3.43	3.43	3.36
Liquid and structural mass	≈ 14.29	14.29	14.85
First bending Frequency	$\approx 1.5Hz$	$3.35Hz$	$7.25Hz$

The experimental campaign consisted of four distinct test types. These can be described as:

- **Tap Tests:** A series of tap tests was performed to determine the frequency responses of the system in various configurations, such as the beam itself, standard, dry mass, and wetted mass configurations.
- **Dry Mass Tests:** A series of dry mass configuration excitation tests, whereby the beam was deflected, rapidly released, and allowed to oscillate until rest was observed.
- **Wetted Tests (Water):** A series of wetted configuration excitation tests utilising water was performed, which were otherwise identical to the aforementioned dry mass tests. Several testing variables were varied during this test and can be found in Table 2.4.
- **Wetted Tests (Kerosene):** A limited series of wetted configuration excitation tests was performed utilising a kerosene substitute with similar density, viscosity and surface tension to kerosene.

The four test types and six listed test variables in Table 2.4 resulted in a total of 61 tests to be conducted within the Protospace experimental campaign.

Table 2.4: Available test variables for Protospace wetted configuration

Test Variable	Values
Fill level	20% \rightarrow 80% (10% increments)
Baffles	Yes / No
Cleaned lid	Yes / No
Ballast mass	0kg \rightarrow 6.5kg
Tank inclination at initial deflection	0° \rightarrow 3.2°
Fluid	Water / Kerosene substitute

Due to the high surface tension of water, drops formed on the upper tank surface on repeated tests. These were found (from visual footage) to influence the growth of slosh instabilities within the system because of the impact of the droplets with the free surface in the first half of the initial oscillation. Therefore, tests were completed with both a clean and a wetted tank ceiling. Additionally, the Protospace campaign aimed to investigate the influence of the simple baffles and the inclination of the tank at the initial tank position (initial beam deflection).

2.3.3 Protospace Experiment Instrumentation

Several sensors were installed to provide reliable experimental data for the beam dynamic response, insight into the fluids flow regime, the resultant slosh loads, and slosh-induced energy dissipation. The readings were recorded operating at 1kHz and maintained synchronous data readings. The following instrumentation was utilised, located at the prescribed locations, and provided the following experimental data:

- **Strain Gauges:** Fixed as close to the beam's neutral axis as possible, providing the bending moment during the free vibration of the beam. The secondary mountings on the front and rear beam flanges allowed for the detection of in-plane oscillations during the experiment. From these, the fundamental bending frequencies could be determined.
- **Accelerometers:** A first pair of accelerometers is located at the beginning and end of the tank span. These accelerometers measure the vertical and lateral (towards the beam root) acceleration of the tank. A second pair of accelerometers, located

at similar span-wise locations are attached to the beam web. The beam tip accelerometer provides a three-axis measurement and shows the in-plane acceleration of the beam and tank. All accelerometers were zeroed for gravity before the test and after the initial beam deflection. The accelerometers allowed for CFD simulations to be run with “applied accelerations”, thus avoiding the complexity of modelling the full beam-tank system.

- **Force Transducers:** Transducers are located at the four attachment points of the tank to the beam. These pre-loaded transducers enabled the forces perpendicular to the tank base being transferred to the beam to be measured. The force measurements were key to comparing CFD-predicted and measured force responses, from which slosh-induced loads and damping energy could be approximated.
- **High-speed Camera:** Finally, a high-speed camera operating at 3000 *fps* allowed the detailed recording of fluid motion in the tank. Of particular interest was the free-surface motion during the experiment.

The provision of excitation kinetics, slosh load data and experimental footage allows for the experimental verification of an employed CFD model, similar to work completed by Craig and Kingsley [33] and by Falsinsen and Timokha [34].

2.4 Initial Results of Protospace Experimental Campaign

The Protospace experimental campaign not only demonstrated the clear energy dissipation and resulting damping effect on the structural responses of sloshing systems but also presented the clear influence of the liquid fill-level on the damping. The greatest damping effect occurred at the 50% fill-level. As shown in Figure 2.3, both the dry and wetted configurations of the Protospace experiment responded with complex behaviour where the first and second bending modes dominated the structural response. Work subsequently conducted by the SLOWD consortium [21, 35, 22] estimated that the 50% test case provided a damping ratio of approximately 7.4%. This is in comparison to the 0.3% damping ratio offered by the structural damping.

Figure 2.3: Selected experimental accelerations for beam-tip accelerometer for various configurations (liquid = water)

This high damping ratio for the 50% fill-level cases is clearly illustrated by Figure 2.3. The slosh-induced energy dissipation results in an accelerated decay in the beams kinetics when compared to the dry mass configuration. Additionally, a phase shift in the excitation frequency is noted from $t = 0.8s$ as a result of the non-linear response of the fluid. An additional finding of the experimental campaign was the lack of noticeable difference in amplitudes and frequencies resulting from the removal of baffles and cleaning of the upper tank surface. Also clear from Figure 2.3 is that the first (largest) frequency of vibration remains constant.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2.4: Footage of interface regimes for the Protospace experiment (a) $t = 0.0s$; (b) $t = 0.12s$; (c) $t = 0.4s$; (d) $t = 1s$; (e) $t = 3s$

With the aid of high-speed camera footage, the nature of the fluid flow during the experimental campaign may be scrutinised. The high initial acceleration provided by the beam on release, the oscillating excitation of the tank and the rapid damping of the beam's kinetics allow for a full range of fluid slosh behaviour to be exhibited. These include liquid-solid impact (Figure 2.4b), aerated flow (Figure 2.4c) and weakly linear slosh (Figure 2.4e).

2.5 Representative Single Degree-of-Freedom Test Case Definition

Figure 2.5: Single degree-of-freedom system

Due to the design of the Protospace experiment (full height baffles and first frequency of excitation remaining constant), a representative test case of an SDOF Protospace compartment (Figure 2.5) undergoing vertical oscillations was created for the purpose of this work. CFD simulations to follow within this study, unless otherwise specified, employ this single compartment tank undergoing a damped sinusoidal vertical acceleration, where the vertical displacement is defined by

$$y(t) = Ae^{-\xi\omega t} (B\cos(\omega t) + C\sin(\omega t)) \quad (2.5)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= 2\pi f \\ A &= \frac{y_0}{\omega^2(\xi^2 + 1)^2} \\ B &= \xi^2 - 1 \\ C &= -2\xi \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Further, f is the excitation frequency of the system in Hz , therefore ω is the excitation frequency of the system in $rad.s^{-1}$ and ξ is the damping coefficient of the SDOF system. This allows for an approximate acceleration definition such that

$$\ddot{y}(t) = y_0\omega^2 e^{-\xi\omega t} \cos(\omega t) \quad (2.7)$$

Where a_1 is the initial tank acceleration, ξ is the damping coefficient and the standard tank geometry as defined below in Figure 2.5 and a fill-level of 50% will be employed. The acceleration signal is derived to ensure that the ratio of free space distance above the fluid to amplitude of the motion is kept constant:

$$\bar{a} = \frac{(1 - \eta)h}{y_0} \quad (2.8)$$

Here η is the fill-level and h is the tank height. This provides a simplified representative case for the Protospace experiment because of the similarities in non-dimensional numbers, as depicted in Table 2.5. The table also compares the aforementioned SDOF system with fluid physics non-dimensional numbers of the full-scale aircraft tank. Quantifying the effect that these differences have on slosh-induced load and -damping will be a key contribution of this thesis.

Table 2.5: Comparison of SDOF system, Protospace and full aircraft fluid non-dimensional properties

	<i>Protospace SDOF</i> (<i>Water</i>)	<i>Protospace</i> (<i>Water</i>)	<i>Aircraft</i> (<i>Cold Kerosene</i>)
$\bar{\rho}$	1.21×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}
Re	459×10^3	476×10^3	149×10^3
We	27.8×10^3	29.8×10^3	337×10^3
Fr	5.86	6.07	2.81

2.6 Closure

This chapter outlined the Protospace experimental campaign and the initial findings of the campaign. The campaign provides an initial attempt to quantify the vertical slosh-induced load and slosh-induced energy dissipation within wing tanks. The experimental results highlights the non-linear damping within an oscillating cantilever due to the presence of the fuel tank, with maximum damping occurring at a fill level of 50%. It further shows that the fundamental frequency of excitation remains constant. The experimental procedure aimed at providing sufficient data for the evaluation of state-of-the-art fluid modelling techniques both to model slosh loads accurately and to quantify slosh-induced energy dissipation.

Chapter 3

High-fidelity Violent Vertical Slosh Modelling

3.1 Introduction

A key novel contribution of this thesis is use of high-fidelity CFD to develop slosh-related non-dimensional scaling laws. This chapter provides a brief exploration of two widely employed methods for accurate high-fidelity free-surface modelling, namely Volume-of-fluids (VOF) and Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) [15]. Selecting a FVM-VOF scheme as the desired method for simulations within this thesis, the governing equations for weakly compressible, isothermal, immiscible two-phase flow is presented. This model is based on recent numerical work [29, 36] that is fully conservative and fully coupled to the VOF equations for two-phase modelling. Following this, a comprehensive energy budget for the total energy is described for an arbitrary enclosed domain undergoing rigid-body acceleration. Following this is a validation of the energy budget for the SDOF system, which includes a mesh independence study for the slosh-induced dissipated energy within the energy budget. The chapter concludes with an investigation of the selected representative SDOF system's sensitivity to Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities.

3.2 State-of-the-Art Slosh Loads Modelling

The modelling of liquid-gas free-surface interaction (sloshing) within tanks and containers is an area of interest within the aerospace industry. This is as it effects aerodynamic stability and aircraft control characteristics during flight and ground manoeuvres.

The high-fidelity modelling of slosh loads and damping requires accurate free-surface modelling (FSM), allowing the simulation of realistic free-surface flow, break-up and

motion. While there are multiple approaches available to model such a system, two industrially viable modelling methods for simulating violent slosh exist, namely, SPH [37] and VOF [16]. Both methods have specific strengths in modelling due to the employment of alternative modelling techniques.

SPH allows FSM and sloshing within a tank employing a Lagrangian-based mesh-free method, utilising particles each representing a portion of the fluid and its resultant properties [38, 39, 40]. SPH allows for large interface deformations and has shown accuracies in simulating free-surface break-up and response, especially in the presence of complex geometries as well as the prediction of slosh-induced pressures [41]. Particles in the domain carry the fluid properties due to the approximation:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) \simeq \sum_i m_i \frac{f_i}{\rho_i} W(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_i|, h) \quad (3.1)$$

For a specific particle, i , the fluid property (density, velocity, or pressure) is calculated by the function f where \mathbf{x} is the co-ordinates of the particle, m and ρ are the mass and density of the particle, respectively, while W is a unique kernel function and h is the kernel function smoothing length. SPH is disadvantaged in slosh loads due to the computational cost and loss in accuracy as particles move. Improved accuracy requires an increased particle count and therefore increases the computational cost. SPH remedies this cost by modelling a single-phase at the risk of neglecting complex phase interactions. Additionally, the basic equation of the SPH Model assumes slip boundary conditions. The implementation of non-slip boundary conditions requires advanced methods such as Ghost Particles, Boundary Particles and Forces, and Bounce Back [16]. Modern developments have continued to mature SPH by means of improved efficiency and the modelling of multi-phase flow [42, 43]. Figure 3.1 displays a single-phase SPH simulation modelling slosh due to an oscillating tank employing the Bounce Back method to achieve a non-slip boundary and indicating the computed static pressure of the liquid [44].

Much of the development of the efficient slosh modelling utilising the SPH method has occurred outside of the scope of the aviation industry. SPH is widely used within naval hydrodynamics [45, 46] for modelling the transport of liquids within ship containers [47]. These techniques have been expanded into the aviation industry to model the transport of fuel within aircraft fuel tanks [15].

Figure 3.1: SPH simulation for baffled Protospace Tank undergoing vertical slosh [48]

VOF currently provides a capable and efficient method of modelling violent free-surface break-up and response [16]. This is provided that surface tension effects down to very small drop sizes are not of key concern, which is the case in this work. By employing a Eulerian representation, VOF allows for accuracy and computational efficiency through the application of standard numerical techniques and a pre-defined mesh to solve the Navier-Stokes equation. The use of this method in numerous commercial CFD codes highlights the desirability of the VOF method. The implementation of a volumetric fraction (α) allows multi-phase FSM simulations, such that the conservation of mass for the liquid in the x direction for a node i is defined as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\alpha\rho_l) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\alpha\rho_l\mathcal{V}_i) = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{\mathcal{V}_l}{\mathcal{V}_l + \mathcal{V}_g} \quad (3.3)$$

Therefore $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ where $\alpha = 1$ denotes the liquid phase and $\alpha = 0.5$ denotes the free-surface. The use of this α -fraction results in a smeared interface representation, which requires costly and complex surface reconstruction if aspects such as interface curvature are critical. Figure 3.2 depicts an example of a FVM-VOF solution from an ELEMENTAL[®] simulation where the liquid is denoted in red and the gas phase in blue.

Figure 3.2: ELEMANTAL[®] FVM-VOF simulation for baffled Protospace Tank undergoing vertical slosh

As such, for this study, the ELEMANTAL[®] finite volume method (FVM) volume-of-fluid (VOF) CFD software is employed as it offers a rigorously validated multi-physics CFD code capable of modelling violent vertical slosh cases [16, 8, 49].

3.3 Volume of Fluids Governing Equations

Consider a control volume (\mathcal{V}) at time (t) within a flow field defined by \mathbf{u} and bounded by a control surface (\mathcal{A}), as depicted in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Sample control volume for derivation

The governing equation for standard VOF method consists of the conservation of incompressible fluid momentum, the conservation of volume fraction and the continuity equation, which are respectively

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \alpha \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) + \rho \mathbf{g} + \gamma \kappa \nabla \alpha \quad (3.6)$$

The addition of a weakly compressible formulation [29, 36] within the conservation of fluid momentum equation yields

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} + \frac{1 - \alpha}{\rho_g} \frac{1}{c_g^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

where \mathbf{u} , ρ , μ , p and g are the fluid velocity, density, dynamic viscosity, pressure and gravitational acceleration. Finally, c_g is the acoustic velocity of the gas phase described by

$$c_g^2 = \frac{\gamma p}{\rho} \quad (3.8)$$

where γ is the gas constant for dry air at Normal Temperature and Pressure (NTP) $\gamma = 1.4$.

The weakly compressible formulation requires the assumption of isentropic compression and expansion as the temperature is not included in the governing equations. Therefore, the density of the gas phase may be computed from the pressure such that

$$\rho_g^{n+1} = \rho_g^n \left(\frac{p^{n+1}}{p^n} \right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \quad (3.9)$$

where n denotes the time-step.

The system is then solved for the transient case utilizing an implicit pressure and explicit velocity discretisation. The introduction of a projected velocity (\mathbf{u}^*) within Equation (3.6) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\rho^{n+1} \mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \rho^{n+1} \mathbf{u}^*}{\Delta t} + \frac{\rho^{n+1} \mathbf{u}^* - \rho^n \mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = & -\nabla p^{n+1} - \nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u} |^n \\ & + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) |^n + \rho \mathbf{g} |^n + \gamma \kappa \nabla \alpha |^n \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

thereby allowing the splitting into

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\rho^{n+1} \mathbf{u}^* - \rho^n \mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = & -\nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u} |^n + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) |^n \\ & + \rho \mathbf{g} |^n + \gamma \kappa \nabla \alpha |^n \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

$$\frac{\rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \rho^{n+1}\mathbf{u}^*}{\Delta t} = -\nabla p^{n+1} \quad (3.12)$$

Equations (3.11) and (3.12) may be adjusted to calculate u^* and u^{n+1} as

$$\mathbf{u}^* = \frac{1}{\rho^{n+1}} [\rho^n \mathbf{u}^n + \Delta t (-\nabla \cdot \rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u})^n + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)^n + \rho \mathbf{g}^n + \gamma \kappa \nabla \alpha^n] \quad (3.13)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho^{n+1}} \nabla p^{n+1} \quad (3.14)$$

Utilising Equation (3.7) and (3.14) provides the weakly compressible Poisson equation:

$$\nabla \cdot u^{n+1} = \nabla \cdot \left(\mathbf{u}^* - \frac{\Delta t}{\rho^{n+1}} \nabla p^{n+1} \right) = -\frac{1 - \alpha^{n+1}}{\gamma p^{n+1}} \frac{p^{n+1} - p^n}{\Delta t} \quad (3.15)$$

This formulation has been incorporated within the ELEMENTAL[®] CFD code solving (3.15) to a predefined tolerance to ensure mass continuity. A predictor-corrector time-stepping scheme is employed to provide the temporal integration within the model to notionally second-order accurate temporal solution. Turbulence is addressed via a large-eddy simulation (LES) Smagorinsky-Lilly model [50] and the liquid-gas interface initialisation is performed to machine precision accuracy via the AGI tool [31].

3.4 Energy Analysis for Violent Slosh Models

The relations employed to estimate slosh-induced energy dissipation are next defined. For the system under consideration the total energy (E_T) budget is considered for this purpose. This is composed of the work done on the fluid by the domain boundary surfaces or surface work (W_s), deformation work (E_{Defo}), kinetic energy (E_k), potential energy (E_u), viscous dissipation (E_{visc}), and surface tension energy (E_{ST}). The full energy budget is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} E_T &= W_s = E_{Defo} + E_k + E_u + E_{visc} + E_{ST} \\ &= E_{Disp} + E_k + E_u + E_{ST} \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

where $E_{Disp} = E_{Defo} + E_{visc}$, where E_{Defo} provides the losses due to liquid impact to the total energy dissipation (as described next).

Consider an enclosed fluid domain containing an immiscible liquid–gas mixture (gas is weakly compressible) undergoing a rigid body linear acceleration of \mathbf{a}_d . The resulting absolute fluid velocity \mathbf{u}_a (velocity relative to earth) can be defined as the sum of the domain velocity (\mathbf{u}_d) and the fluid velocity (\mathbf{u}) relative to the non-inertial reference frame (CFD mesh reference frame), therefore $\mathbf{u}_a = \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{u}_d$. For incompressible flow the momentum conservation of the fluid is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D}{Dt}(\rho\mathbf{u}_a) &= \left[\frac{\partial\rho\mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) + \rho\mathbf{a}_d \right] \\ &= -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T) + \rho\mathbf{g} + \gamma\kappa\nabla\alpha \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

where p is pressure, t is time, α is VOF volume fraction. For the purpose of numerical solution and the fluid domain is subdivided into volumes \mathcal{V} . Total energy conservation results from taking the dot product of Equation (3.17) with the volume-averaged $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_a$ followed by integration over space and time (includes integration by parts of the pressure term):

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} \left[\frac{\partial\rho\mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) + \rho\mathbf{a}_d \right] dV dt &= \\ - \int_0^t \mathbf{u}_d \cdot \int_{\mathcal{A}_d} p\mathbf{n}d\mathcal{A}dt & \\ + \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} [\nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T)] dV dt & \\ + \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} \rho\mathbf{g}dV dt + \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} \gamma\kappa\nabla\alpha dV dt & \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

where \mathcal{A} is the surface of all mesh finite volumes \mathcal{V} , \mathbf{n} is the outwards pointing normal, and $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_a$ is the volume averaged absolute velocity and is employed as the dot product of the energy terms to establish an energy norm which is exactly consistent with the finite volume discretisation of the momentum equation. Note that the instantaneous power may be computed by omitting the integration over time in (3.18). Further \mathcal{A}_d is the fluid domain bounding surface. The terms in Equation (3.18) contain the different forms of energy:

$$W_s = - \int_0^t \mathbf{u}_d \cdot \int_{\mathcal{A}_d} [p - \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)] \mathbf{n} d\mathcal{A} dt = \int_0^t \mathbf{u}_d \cdot \mathbf{F} dt \quad (3.19)$$

$$E_u = - \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} \rho \mathbf{g} dV dt \quad (3.20)$$

$$E_k = \int_{\mathcal{V}} \frac{1}{2} \rho \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a dV \quad (3.21)$$

$$E_{Defo} = \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} \left[\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) + \rho \mathbf{a}_d \right] dV dt - E_k \quad (3.22)$$

$$E_{visc} = - \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} \nabla \cdot \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) dV dt + W_{s\mu} \quad (3.23)$$

$$E_{ST} = - \int_0^t \bar{\mathbf{u}}_a \cdot \int_{\mathcal{V}} \gamma \kappa \nabla \alpha dV dt \quad (3.24)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the force from the tank onto the liquid, $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ is the time-averaged velocity and $W_{s\mu}$ is the domain boundary viscous work component included in (3.19). In the above the force is computed via the following expression,

$$\mathbf{F} = - \int_{\mathcal{A}_d} [p - \mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)] \mathbf{n} d\mathcal{A} \quad (3.25)$$

which is used for the CFD load calculations. A similar energy budget has successfully been tabled for SPH simulations by Marrone *et al.* [51, 52]

The reason for subtracting the kinetic energy term from the first integral in (3.22) is to account for the liquid impact related losses (assuming initial fluid velocities of $\mathbf{u}_a^0 = 0$). These impact losses (liquid-liquid or liquid-wall) have been shown by Antuono *et al.* [53] and Marrone *et al.* [54] to be accounted for by the liquid incompressible pressure-poisson fractional step (Equation (3.15)) employed in the ELEMENTAL[®] solver [49].

From the above, it is instructive to note that E_{Disp} for one tank oscillation cycle (one period) may also be approximated from experimentally measured data as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{Disp} &= W_s - E_k - E_u \\ &\approx \int_0^t \mathbf{u}_d \cdot \mathbf{F} dt - \frac{1}{2} m_f \mathbf{u}_d \cdot \mathbf{u}_d - \int_0^t m_f \mathbf{u}_d \cdot \mathbf{g} dt \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

where m_f is the fluid mass in the tank and \mathbf{F} is the force of the tank on the fluid (which may be inferred from load cell measurements). This is provided that accurate temporal tank position (displacement) data are available and noting that it was found that E_{ST} accounts for less than 1% of the energy budget.

3.4.1 Energy Budget Normalisation

To enable direct comparison (plotting on the same graph) of computed energy budget and slosh loads for different excitation frequencies and liquid masses (as will be done later in the thesis), normalisation is required. Hence, the computed energy dissipated (E_{Disp}) and work in (W_s) are normalised to the final change in potential energy of a simulation (E_u). Further, computed vertical slosh force (F_y) is normalised and oscillation count (n) is employed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}|| &= \frac{E_{Disp}}{E_u} \\ ||W_s|| &= \frac{W_s}{E_u} \\ ||F_y|| &= \frac{F_y}{|F_y(t=0)|} \\ n &= \frac{t}{\omega} \end{aligned} \tag{3.27}$$

where ω is the frequency of excitation for a single-degree of freedom (SDOF) system. This normalisation assumes a final change in potential energy (E_u), however this may be modified to utilise an alternative E_u value for the normalisation.

3.5 Evaluation of Two-Dimensional Energy Analysis

Employing the standard definitions described above enables the accurate evaluation of the energy balance previously derived. Considering a 2D standard SDOF tank filled with water at STP oscillating at $7Hz$ with an initial acceleration $a_1 = 200m.s^{-2}$ and a damping coefficient of $\xi = 0.06$ results in $y(end) = 0.1023m$ and a normalising potential energy of $E_u = 3.01W$. Therefore, Figure 3.4 graphs the typical normalised energy results for the system over the first 3 oscillations for a 2D Cartesian mesh. Notice that the deformation energy (liquid impact-induced dissipation) is predicted to be considerably larger than the viscous dissipation.

Figure 3.4: Energy budget for SDOF system $\Delta x = 3.33 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mm}$

Figure 3.5 provides the energy dissipation over the 3 oscillations. Figure 3.6 depicts the fluid flow evolution against the dissipated energy across the 3 oscillations of the system. The figures depict the specific slosh regimes namely the collapse of the free surface meniscus due to the initial vertical acceleration of the tank (Figure 3.6a), Rayleigh-Taylor instability that ensues on the first negative acceleration (Figure 3.6b), initial fluid-tank impact with the top surface of the tank (Figure 3.6c), the secondary fluid-tank impact with the base of the tank (Figure 3.6d) and finally development of fully aerated slosh flow (Figure 3.6e). Figure 3.6 indicates the volume fraction of the VOF field as defined by Equation (3.3).

Figure 3.5: Energy dissipation for $\Delta x = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}$

Figure 3.6: Fluid response at various times within Figure 3.5 for $\Delta x = 5 \times 10^{-4}m$ () (a) $t = 0.034s$; (b) $t = 0.069s$; (c) $t = 0.086s$; (d) $t = 0.15s$; (e) $t = 0.33s$

3.6 Rayleigh-Taylor Instability for Purely Vertical Slosh

A concern when modelling purely vertical excitations is the sensitivity of the interface to Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities. Note this does not refer to the formal theory of Rayleigh-Taylor instability analysis but the phenomena, which occurs at the interface between two

liquids of varying densities, where the light fluid pushes through the heavier fluid [55]. This occurs particularly during the first downward acceleration of the tank. This is contrary to popular belief for high Weber number flows, and it is due to the collapse of the initial liquid meniscus when undergoing large upward accelerations ($10g$). Therefore, the free surface within the CFD simulations employs an analytical meniscus definition to capture the same phenomena, an analytical free surface definition for this meniscus is to follow and is visible at the fluid-solid boundary interface (See Figure 3.7 (d)).

Figure 3.7: Influence of meniscus inclusion on fluid response within single-degree of freedom system (a - c) Flat free-surface; (d - f) Meniscus incorporated

Figure 3.8: Meniscus of free-surface for a single wall contact

For a 2D tank (large depth), the initial free-surface definition of a meniscus may be derived analytically by considering the intersection of a fluid-gas free-surface with a single solid wall, such as depicted by Figure 3.8. In the figure, $y(x)$ is the height of the free surface at position x , the solid wall interface is found at $x = 0$ and θ is the contact angle.

The free-surface exists such that as $x \rightarrow \infty, y(x) \rightarrow 0$. The liquid interface curvature is defined as [56]

$$\kappa = \frac{\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2\right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (3.28)$$

At any position along the interface the following pressure relationship exists across the interface:

$$p_g - p_l = \frac{\gamma}{\kappa} \quad (3.29)$$

where p is pressure, the g and l subscripts represent the gaseous and liquid stages respectively and γ is surface tension. Assuming constant pressure in the gas and the liquid pressure resulting from static pressure under gravity, Equations (3.28) and (3.29) can be combined such that

$$\frac{\gamma \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2\right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} = p_g - (p_g - \rho_l g y) \quad (3.30)$$

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = \frac{\rho_l g y}{\gamma} \left[1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2\right]^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (3.31)$$

This non-linear differential equation may then be solved numerically to provide an analytical location of the free-surface due to the meniscus at one wall. An additional approximation that $\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2 \ll 1$ enables the simplification to

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = \frac{\rho_l g y}{\gamma} \quad (3.32)$$

where the general solution to the differential equation is given by

$$y(x) = \cot(\theta) \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{\rho_l g}} e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\rho_l g}{\gamma}} x} \quad (3.33)$$

Therefore the boundary condition at $x = 0$ is determined to be

$$y(0) = \cot(\theta) \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{\rho_l g}} \quad (3.34)$$

In the case where two opposing walls are located at b and $-b$ the fluid free surface may be expressed as

$$y(x) = \frac{\cot(\theta)}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{\rho_l g}} \frac{1}{\sinh\left(\sqrt{\frac{\rho_l g}{\gamma}} b\right)} \left(e^{\sqrt{\frac{\rho_l g}{\gamma}} x} + e^{-\sqrt{\frac{\rho_l g}{\gamma}} x}\right) \quad (3.35)$$

Equation (3.35) has been employed within this thesis to initiate the analytical free-surface meniscus in both 2D and 3D simulations.

3.7 Closure

This chapter provided a brief overview of both VOF and SPH as methods for accurate high-fidelity free-surface modelling. Selecting FVM-VOF as the desired modelling tool within this thesis, the governing equations for a weakly-compressible FVM-VOF based CFD scheme is presented for use for all simulations. Utilising this weakly-compressible scheme, a comprehensive energy budget for the quantification of the slosh-induced energy dissipation for a two-phase immiscible fluid system can be defined. Finally, the

importance of accounting for Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities due to the presence of a liquid meniscus is demonstrated and the function used in this work to initialise the liquid interface can be developed.

Chapter 4

High-fidelity Violent Slosh CFD Validation

4.1 Introduction

The proposed use of ELEMENTAL[®] for accurate modelling of both slosh loads and slosh-induced energy dissipation requires the validation of the CFD model against experimental data. This chapter presents the derivation of the kinetic profile for the selected Protospace Experiment from the experimental readings. ELEMENTAL[®] 2D simulations are then validated for the modelling of the selected Protospace case and a mesh independence study is then completed. Finally, the chapter concludes by investigating the influence of 3D effects on the slosh loads and slosh-induced energy dissipation for modelling the representative case.

4.2 Protospace Experiment Data Processing

Within the simulations to follow, the tank is modelled in isolation employing the accelerometer readings from the tank base to develop a three degree-of-freedom (DoF) excitation profile to apply to the simulated tank. The simulation may then be validated against the experimental force reading (the sum of readings from Force transducers once corrected for pre-load). Additionally, the presence of a high-speed camera footage allows for the qualitative comparison of the simulated free surface against the experimental footage.

The generation of the three DoF excitation profile (vertical and lateral translations with a rotation about the in-plane axis) for the simulation requires the definition of a suitable reference frame. A non-inertial reference frame for the tank domain allows for the translation and rotation of the tank structure to be incorporated with ease.

Figure 4.1: Non-inertial reference frame for particle p

An individual particle denoted by p , as depicted in Figure 4.1, can move relative to the non-inertial frame (\hat{e}_i, \hat{e}_j) with origin at b . The non-inertial reference frame in turn undergoes rotation and translation relative to the inertial reference frame (\hat{e}_x, \hat{e}_y) , where gravity is denoted by \mathbf{g} acting in according to the inertial reference frame. Here \mathbf{r}_p and \mathbf{r}_b denote the position of p and b in relation to (\hat{e}_x, \hat{e}_y) respectively. Finally, $\mathbf{r}_{p/b}$ denotes the position of p according to (\hat{e}_i, \hat{e}_j) . Therefore \mathbf{r}_p may be denoted as

$$\mathbf{r}_{p/A} = \mathbf{r}_{b/A} + \mathbf{r}_{p/b} \quad (4.1)$$

Taking time derivatives of Equation (4.1) [57] allows the definition of the particle's velocity and acceleration relative to (\hat{e}_x, \hat{e}_y) as

$$\mathbf{u}_{p/A} = \mathbf{u}_{b/A} + \mathbf{u}_{p/b} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{p/A} = \mathbf{a}_{b/A} + \mathbf{a}_{p/b} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b}) + 2\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{u}_{p/b} \quad (4.3)$$

The excitation signal for the simulation can be derived from Equations (4.2) and (4.3) by means of assuming b and p to lie on the tank (see Figure 4.2). This allows the assumption of $\mathbf{r}_{p/b}$ to be replaced by a rigid body with a fixed length l (the measured distance between the two accelerometers) and therefore allowing $\mathbf{u}_{p/b} = \mathbf{a}_{p/b} = 0$.

Figure 4.2: Experimental accelerations available from Protospace campaign

As depicted in Figure 4.2, the Protospace experimental set-up provides $\mathbf{a}_{b/A} = a_{bx/A}\hat{e}_x + a_{by/A}\hat{e}_y$ and $\mathbf{a}_{p/A} = a_{px/A}\hat{e}_x + a_{py/A}\hat{e}_y$, where $a_{p/A}$ and $a_{b/A}$ are the net accelerations at points p and b due to both the lateral and rotational kinetics of the system. The experiment was tightly controlled to avoid out-of-plane motion of the beam, thereby allowing the simplification where $a_{pz} = a_{bz} = 0$.

Figure 4.3: Proposed excitation profile for Protospace modelling campaign

Employing (4.3) for the rigid body assumption of $\mathbf{r}_{p/b}$ enables the calculation of the four DoF excitation profile as depicted in Figure 4.3, such that the acceleration is calculated as

$$\mathbf{a}'_{b/A} = \mathbf{a}_{b/A} + \mathbf{g}_A \quad (4.4)$$

where \mathbf{g}_A provides the correction for the re-inclusion of gravity. Going forward, it is implied that all acceleration terms are written in the non-inertial basis (ie. b), as this is the basis in which the accelerometers measure. The rotational components may be calculated as:

$$\mathbf{a}'_{p/A} = \mathbf{a}'_{b/A} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b}) \quad (4.5)$$

Due to the experimental constraints $\omega_{bx} = \omega_{by} = 0$, therefore

$$\begin{bmatrix} a'_{px/A} \\ a'_{py/A} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a'_{bx/A} \\ a'_{by/A} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \dot{\omega}_{bz}l \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\omega_{bz}^2 l \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.6)$$

This system may then be separated into two unique equations:

$$a'_{px/A} = a'_{bx/A} - \omega_{bz}^2 l \quad (4.7)$$

$$a'_{py/A} = a'_{by/A} + \dot{\omega}_{bz}l \quad (4.8)$$

Solving for ω_{bz} and $\dot{\omega}_{bz}$ provides the following solutions:

$$\omega_{bz} = \sqrt{\frac{a'_{bx/A} - a'_{px/A}}{l}} \quad (4.9)$$

$$\dot{\omega}_{bz} = \frac{a'_{py/A} - a'_{by/A}}{l} \quad (4.10)$$

The full derivation of these terms is presented in Appendix A.1.

The gravitational acceleration in the CFD code is always written relative to the non-inertial reference frame. Therefore the accurate calculation of the gravitational vector requires the calculation of the tank inclination (β_{Tank}), which is a function of the beam-tip displacement (Δy_{Tip}) and beam length (l_{Beam}). Note that this is specifically not computed via double integration of the measured accelerations due to the resulting numerical errors accumulating after thousands of time-steps. Assuming the beam's kinetic response remains linear as $\Delta y_{Tip} \ll l_{Beam}$ ($\max(|\Delta y_{Tip}|) = 0.045m$ and $l_{Beam} = 2.35m$), it can be assumed that

$$\Delta y_{Tip}(t) \approx c_1 \epsilon_{Beam}(t) \quad (4.11)$$

$$\beta_{Tank}(t) \approx c_2 \Delta y_{Tip}(t) + c_3 \quad (4.12)$$

where ϵ_{Beam} is the strain measured by the beam-mounted strain gauges, c_1 and c_2 account for the beam initial deflection, and c_3 allows for $\beta_{Tank}(0) = 0$. c_1 is estimated by means of the initial offset of the beam's tip such that $c_1 = \frac{\Delta y_{Tip}(0)}{\epsilon_{Beam}(0)}$. The constants c_2 and c_3 are estimated by means of a similar methodology.

4.3 Violent Slosh CFD Simulations

The utilisation of FVM-VOF CFD within the study requires accurate, high-fidelity, mesh independent simulations. Specifically, the accuracy with regard to the predicted slosh

force is critical as this is the key uncertainty when quantifying slosh-induced energy dissipation in this work (see Equation (3.26)). This is due to this work involving prescribed tank motions (obtained from measurements). The FVM-VOF CFD code ELEMENTAL[®] has been employed extensively to model violent slosh [49, 8]. Turbulence is modelled via Large-eddy simulation (LES) employing the Smagorinsky-Lilly model [50] and a weakly compressible gas model [36, 29] is employed, while the VOF field initialisation is performed to machine-precision accuracy via the AGI tool [31]. The Protospace experimental campaign provides suitable experimental data to validate ELEMENTAL[®] through modelling the 50% fill-level Protospace experiment [22]. This involves applying the measured tank acceleration profile as per Section 4.2 and comparing the simulated forces and the experimental forces measured.

4.3.1 Evaluation of Two-Dimensional Simulations

Figure 4.4: CFD-predicted interface regimes at different times for the seven-compartment Protospace 2D simulation case for $\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$

In the interest of computational efficiency, the initial validation study of ELEMENTAL[®] in-

volved the modelling of the Protospace experimental campaign in 2D. Using the measured tank accelerations from the experiment as input, CFD simulations were performed on a range of different mesh spacings. The coarsest and finest mesh considered within the study are $\Delta x = 1.25 \times 10^{-3}m$ and $\Delta x = 3.33 \times 10^{-4}m$ respectively. For a selected mesh ($\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$) the 2D CFD-predicted free-surface interface at various times is depicted in Figure 4.4. These may be compared to experimental footage (Figure 2.4). As shown, a range of different slosh regimes are present. These include liquid-solid impact (Figures 2.4b & 4.4b), aerated flow (Figures 2.4c & 4.4c) and weakly linear slosh (Figures 2.4e & 4.4e).

Figure 4.5: Experimental vs 2D ELEMENTAL[®] simulated vertical slosh loads

Figure 4.6: Experimental vs 2D ELEMENTAL[®] simulated slosh-induced energy dissipation

Figure 4.5 compares the measured and CFD-predicted vertical slosh loads (see Equation (3.25)) for Cartesian meshes. For the initial 0.4s the force peak and dissipation is under-predicted for all mesh spacings, this may result from unreported experimental uncertainty within the Protospace experimental results. Completing an error analysis and mesh sensitivity study provides Table 4.1 and Figure 4.7. Where $\|\epsilon_F\|_2$ is the euclidean norm of the error percentage such that,

$$\epsilon_F(t) = \frac{100 \times |F_{CFD}(t) - F_{Exp}(t)|}{\max(|F_{Exp}|)} \quad (4.13)$$

$$\|\epsilon_F\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_F(t_0)^2 + \epsilon_F(t_1)^2 + \dots + \epsilon_F(t_n)^2}{n}}$$

This highlights a linear asymptotic in the euclidean norm error is found for $\Delta x \leq 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$. Similarly, Figure 4.6 compares the measured and CFD slosh-induced energy dissipation, as per Equation (3.26). At the end of the simulation, the final simulated slosh-induced energy dissipation is found to deviate from the experimental value by a maximum of 3.66% for $\Delta x \leq 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$.

Table 4.1: Force error analysis for ELEMENTAL[®] Protospace modelling as a function of mesh spacing

Δx [m]	$\ \epsilon_F\ _2$ [%]
1.25×10^{-3}	1.97
1×10^{-3}	1.61
6.67×10^{-4}	1.37
5×10^{-4}	1.28
4×10^{-4}	1.25
3.33×10^{-4}	1.23

Figure 4.7: Percentage difference between 2D ELEMENTAL[®] predicted and experimentally derived slosh-induced loads for various mesh resolutions

4.3.2 Evaluation of Three-Dimensional Simulations

To evaluate three-dimensional effects within the modelling of the SLOWD Protospace experiment, the simulations for 3D simulations are also run, using a Cartesian mesh with spacing $\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$. The 3D mesh is with a depth of $0.11m$ as per the Protospace experimental design. ELEMENTAL[®] provides a 3D FVM-VOF simulation with forces in all cartesian planes and moments about the origin. A comparison of the vertical slosh loads and slosh-induced energy dissipation between the 2D and 3D cases are presented by Figures 4.8 and 4.9 respectively. Completing an error analysis for the slosh loads within Table 4.2 is calculated by means of Equation (4.13). This calculation shows the minimal changes in the force error between the 2D and 3D simulations. Figure 4.9 highlights the small increase in the slosh-induced energy dissipation found within 3D simulations. Figure 4.10 presents a comparison of the 3D CFD-predicted free-surface interface at various times, which may be compared to Figures 2.4 and 4.4.

Figure 4.8: Experimental vs 2D & 3D ELEMENTAL[®] simulated vertical slosh loads for $\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$

Figure 4.9: Experimental vs 2D & 3D ELEMENTAL[®] simulated slosh-induced energy dissipation for $\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$

Table 4.2: Force error analysis for ELEMENTAL[®] Protospace modelling for 2D and 3D cases $\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$

	$\ \epsilon_F\ _2$ [%]
2D	1.37
3D	1.23

Figure 4.10: CFD-predicted interface regimes at different times for the seven-compartment Protospace 3D simulation case for $\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$ with a cut plane through the y-z axis plane of the tank

The minimal changes between the 2D and 3D simulations prove the reliability of 2D simulations in modelling global slosh loads and slosh-induced energy dissipation for the case under consideration. As a result, subsequent simulations will employ the 2D model for global load analyses.

4.4 Validation of Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) Model

The SLOWD Project [58] included a detailed study of the ability of both SPH and VOF methods to model all energy dissipation mechanisms within the fluid flow accurately. One such area of interest is the mesh resolution required for the Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) Smagorinsky-Lilly model to simulate the violent slosh with the Protospace Experimental

campaign accurately ($Re \sim 455 \times 10^3$). To this end, the kinetic energy dissipation rate per a unit mass (ε) and turbulent kinetic energy per a unit mass (k_{Turb}) needs to be estimated for a system with similar Re where the fluid is assumed to be fully turbulent.

For this purpose we employ the SDOF system described in Section 2.5 [58, 59, 24] with excitation given by Equation (2.7) where $a_1 = 200m.s^{-2}$ and $f = 7Hz$. The use of LES to model turbulence requires the estimation of both the scale of the large energetic eddies (l_{eddy}) and the Taylor micro-scale (λ_{LES}) [60], as this informs the required mesh resolution.

The scale of the large energetic eddies can be evaluated as

$$l_{eddy} = \frac{k_{Turb}^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\varepsilon} \approx 0.06m \quad (4.14)$$

which is comparable to the full height of the tank.

The Taylor micro-scale (λ_{LES}) provides the length scale below which the relevance of viscous effects impacts the flow evolution. Therefore, the spatial filter should be smaller than λ_{LES} which allows the resolution of the main turbulent eddies [61]. λ_{LES} for the fluid phase is calculated as [62]

$$\lambda_{LES} = \sqrt{\frac{10\nu k_{Turb}}{\varepsilon}} \approx 4 \times 10^{-4}m \quad (4.15)$$

where ν is the fluid kinematic viscosity.

Figure 4.11 displays the viscosity ratio within the tank ($\frac{\mu_t}{\mu}$) over the course of the simulation for a mesh where $\Delta x > \lambda_{LES}$ and $\Delta x = \lambda_{LES}$. Though the upper limit of $\frac{\mu_t}{\mu} = 10$ is somewhat high to claim a fully resolved simulation, it is to be noted, the energy dissipation due turbulence was found to be much smaller than the impact-induced dissipation (see Figure 3.4). As such, the absolute accuracy of turbulence modelling is of less importance. LES will nonetheless be employed in all remaining simulations unless otherwise specified.

Figure 4.11: Large-eddy simulation model viscosity ratio for SDOF simulation, fluid free-surface depicted by contour (a - c) $\Delta x = 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m > \lambda_{LES}$; (d - f) $\Delta x = \lambda_{LES} = 4 \times 10^{-4}m$

4.5 Closure

This chapter detailed the verification and validation of the ELEMENTAL[®] FVM-VOF modelling tool for the prediction of vertical slosh-induced forces and dissipation. It demonstrated a correlation between predicted and measured slosh loads of 98% for both 2D and 3D simulations. The computed dissipated energy was within 96% of the measured values. This therefore demonstrates the suitability of the 2D model for the derivation of slosh-related scaling parameters, which now follow.

The 2D simulations also provide a reasonable correlation between the 2D CFD-predicted free-surface interface and the experimental imagery. For the modelling of

the Protospace experimental campaign, linear error convergence was achieved for $\Delta x \leq 6.67 \times 10^{-4}m$. Similar accuracies are found to exist when utilising 2D and 3D simulations, thereby allowing for the use of 2D simulations for this project.

The chapter concludes with an evaluation of the LES model for modelling violent sloshing cases with similar Reynolds and Froude numbers. This informs suitable CFD mesh spacing.

Chapter 5

CFD-Based Non-Dimensional Analysis of Vertical Slosh

5.1 Introduction

A key contribution of this thesis is to develop the quantitative relationship between fluid physics-related non-dimensional numbers and vertical slosh-induced damping. These are referred to as so-called “scaling laws”. Therefore, this chapter details a non-dimensional analysis of a SDOF tank system. The theory behind Buckingham’s Π -theorem is briefly presented, followed by the dimensional analysis of the SDOF system in terms of the resulting flow physics-related non-dimensional parameters. This is followed by quantifying the influence of these non-dimensional numbers on slosh load and energy dissipation.

5.2 Non-Dimensional Analysis through Buckingham Π Theorem

Non-dimensional analysis offers a method of simplifying complex systems or behaviours, increasing the understanding of the systems before experimental and quantitative analyses of the selected complex behaviour [63]. The system is simplified by reducing the degrees of freedom for a system to a selected number and thereby allowing for increased manageability and the ability to define quantitative relationships and scaling laws that would otherwise be obscured by the complexity of the system [64]. The Buckingham Π theorem [65] enables the determination of a set of dimensionless properties that influence a specific parameter within a complex system, without the need for the form of the final governing equation to be known. The theorem aims to identify a function utilising the

identified dimensionless properties to define the chosen parameter.

The theorem specifies that a quantity (Q_0) may be defined by n independent quantities within the system (Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_n). In this way, the dimensional subset consisting of k ranks may be used to normalise the independent quantities, providing $n - k$ dimensionless degrees-of-freedom for the system ($\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \dots, \Pi_{n-k}$), thereby allowing the definition of a function (such as slosh damping) such that

$$Q_0 = f(\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \dots, \Pi_{n-k}) \quad (5.1)$$

Changes to the function may then be effected by altering of the dimensionless quantities, for example:

$$\Pi'_1 = \Pi_1 \times \Pi_* \quad (5.2)$$

where $\Pi_* \in (\Pi_2, \Pi_3, \dots, \Pi_{n-k})$ and Π'_1 then replaces Π_1 within the function. This has allowed for the modification of the initial function to utilise conventional non-dimensional numbers. This is particularly useful in fluid mechanics because of the number of dimensionless quantities and the evolution and nature of flow according to these specific dimensionless quantities.

5.3 Non-Dimensional Analysis of SDOF Sloshing System

Consider a sloshing system employing the SDOF system as defined within Section 2.5 which is representative dimensionally of the Protospace experimental setup. As such the vertical oscillation (SDOF) of a rectangular 2D tank (single Protospace compartment) is supported by a mass-spring-damper system with a spring constant k and damper constant c , as described in Section 2.5. All simulations employ air at standard atmospheric conditions as the gas within the liquid-gas slosh system. The 14 parameters considered relevant to the dimensional analysis are presented in Table 5.1. Also included are entries of the dimensional matrix for the units of Mass (M in kg), Length (L in m) and Time (T in s).

Table 5.1: Dimensional matrix

Quantity			Units		
			<i>M</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>T</i>
μ	Liquid Dynamic Viscosity	$[Pa.s]$	1	-1	-1
ρ	Liquid Density	$[kg.m^{-3}]$	1	-3	0
ρ_{air}	Gas Density	$[kg.m^{-3}]$	1	-3	0
γ	Liquid Surface Tension	$[N.m^{-1}]$	1	0	-2
θ	Liquid–solid Contact Angle	$[rads]$	0	0	0
v	Fluid Speed	$[m.s^{-1}]$	0	1	-1
g	Gravity	$[m.s^{-2}]$	0	1	-2
m	Solid Mass	$[kg]$	1	0	0
k	Structural Stiffness	$[N.m^{-1}]$	1	0	-2
c	Structural Damping	$[Ns.m^{-1}]$	1	0	-1
h	Tank Height	$[m]$	0	1	0
l	Tank Length	$[m]$	0	1	0
η_0	Height of Fluid	$[m]$	0	1	0
y_0	Initial Tank Offset (spring displacement)	$[m]$	0	1	0

The rank 3-dimensional matrix employs the normalisation of length (h), which is tank height, mass (ρh^3) and time ($\frac{h}{v}$), where v is the tank speed. Therefore the application of the Buckingham II Theorem leads to $14 - 3 = 11$ dimensionless groups.

Table 5.2: Normalised quantities

Quantity	Normalisation	Quantity	Normalisation
Π_1 m	$m \left(\frac{1}{\rho h^3} \right)$	Π_7 c	$c \left(\frac{1}{\rho h^3} \right) \left(\frac{h}{v} \right)$
Π_2 ρ_{air}	$\rho_{air} \left(\frac{1}{\rho h^3} \right) (h^3)$	Π_8 θ	
Π_3 μ	$\mu \left(\frac{1}{\rho h^3} \right) (h) \left(\frac{h}{v} \right)$	Π_9 l	$l \left(\frac{1}{h} \right)$
Π_4 g	$g \left(\frac{h}{v} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{h} \right)$	Π_{10} η_0	$\eta_0 \left(\frac{1}{h} \right)$
Π_5 γ	$\gamma \left(\frac{1}{\rho h^3} \right) \left(\frac{h}{v} \right)^2$	Π_{11} y_0	$y_0 \left(\frac{1}{h} \right)$
Π_6 k	$k \left(\frac{1}{\rho h^3} \right) \left(\frac{h}{v} \right)^2$		

The Π_1 group is of the order solid to liquid mass ratio \bar{m} of the one-degree of freedom system. Π_2 is the density ratio $\bar{\rho}$ of the gas and liquid phase in the tank. Π_3 to Π_5 are

well-known flow physics related dimensionless numbers, namely Reynolds, Froude and Weber. Note that the v subscript is added to the latter to denote the standard definition based on the fluid speed.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Pi_1 &= \frac{m}{\rho h^3} = \bar{m} & \Pi_2 &= \frac{\rho_{Air}}{\rho} = \bar{\rho} & \Pi_3 &= \frac{\rho v h}{\mu} = Re_v \\
 \Pi_4 &= \frac{v}{\sqrt{gh}} = Fr_v & \Pi_5 &= \frac{\rho v^2 h}{\gamma} = We_v & \Pi_6 &= \frac{k}{\rho h^3} \left(\frac{h}{v}\right)^2 \\
 \Pi_7 &= \frac{c}{\rho h^3} \frac{h}{v} & \Pi_8 &= \theta & \Pi_9 &= \frac{l}{h} = \tilde{A} \\
 \Pi_{10} &= \frac{\eta_0}{h} = \tilde{F} & \Pi_{11} &= \frac{y_0}{h} = \tilde{Y}_0
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.3}$$

As we are considering harmonic tank motion, it is convenient to express the fluid non-dimensional numbers in terms of excitation frequency instead of tank speed:

$$v \sim \omega y_0 \tag{5.4}$$

This is done because in this work the magnitude of tank displacement is of a similar order to the tank height. Equation (5.4) is relevant as from experimental observation the first two to three cycles of oscillation are representative of the slosh-induced energy dissipation potential for the violent slosh under consideration. Hence only the first 3 excitation cycles are considered for the non-dimensional scaling calculations (to follow) as these are representative of peak loads and slosh-induced dissipation. Therefore Π_3 to Π_5 may be modified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Pi'_3 &= \frac{\rho \omega y_0 h}{\mu} = Re \\
 \Pi'_4 &= \frac{\omega y_0}{\sqrt{gh}} = Fr \\
 \Pi'_5 &= \frac{\rho \omega^2 y_0^2 h}{\gamma} = We
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.5}$$

where Re , Fr and We are the excitation frequency-based Reynolds, Froude and Weber numbers, respectively. The Froude number as a function of the frequency parameter therefore infers a reduced frequency or a Strouhal number, which represents the ratio of the characteristic time of the mechanical system and the fluid-characteristic time. Finally, we manipulate Π_6 and Π_7 by combining them with Π_1 :

$$\begin{aligned}\Pi'_6 &= \sqrt{\frac{\Pi_6}{\Pi_1}} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m} \frac{h}{v}} = \frac{\omega_n}{\omega} = \omega_r \\ \Pi'_7 &= \frac{\Pi_7}{2\Pi_1\Pi'_6} = \frac{c}{2m\omega_n} = \xi_d\end{aligned}\tag{5.6}$$

The above is achieved by employing the standard definitions of the structural natural frequency of excitation ω_n and the structural damping ratio ξ_d for harmonic oscillators, where:

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}\tag{5.7}$$

and

$$\xi_d = \frac{c}{2m\omega_n}\tag{5.8}$$

Further, ω_r denotes the reduced frequency of the system (structure and slosh).

Π_9 , Π_{10} and Π_{11} are derived by dividing all other relevant geometrical quantities by the characteristic length, thereby enforcing h (tank height) as the characteristic length. The resulting \tilde{A} is the tank aspect ratio, \tilde{F} is the liquid fill ratio and \tilde{Y}_0 is the dimensionless initial deflection of the mass-spring system.

The derivation of a functional relationship to characterise the fluid-structure-system-damping will employ the resulting π groups:

$$\xi = f\left(\bar{m}, \omega_r, \bar{\rho}, Re, Fr, We, \theta, \tilde{A}, \tilde{F}, \tilde{Y}_0\right)\tag{5.9}$$

The total system damping ξ can be decomposed into its two parts:

$$\xi = \xi_d + \Delta\xi_s\tag{5.10}$$

where ξ_d and $\Delta\xi_s$ are the damping due to the structure (dry) and slosh damping. To focus the analysis on the slosh-induced damping via prescribed tank motion, therefore the value of ξ is prescribed (the chosen value will be motivated when used in the relevant sections to follow and keep the geometry unchanged), such that the derivation of a functional relationship characterising the slosh damping results in the form:

$$\Delta\xi_s = f_1(\bar{\rho}, Re, Fr, We, \theta)\tag{5.11}$$

From the above, it is possible to identify three distinct groups of dimensionless numbers influencing the slosh damping within the SDOF system. The three groups are flow

physics (fluid specific non-dimensional numbers such as $\bar{\rho}$, Re , Fr , We and θ), fluid-structure interactions (FSI) and geometric non-dimensional factors. A key contribution of this work is to use high-fidelity FVM-VOF CFD to quantify the influence of the aforementioned fluid physics related non-dimensional numbers on slosh load and damping. The geometric dimensionless numbers will remain unchanged (due to dimensional similarity with the full-scale) while tank excitation is inferred via the Fr number (due to ω).

5.4 Non-Dimensional Property Parameter Space

The intended aim of the Protospace experiment [22] was to provide a Froude-scaled aircraft wing with a geometry scaling of $\lambda = 0.2$ while employing water, whereas the full-scale model makes use of cold kerosene. The calculated non-dimensional values for the Froude-scaled Protospace (employing kerosene), actual Protospace (as achieved in the experimental campaign employing water) and the full-scale model are given in Table 5.3. Accordingly, the range of the non-dimensional parameter space for which to build the scaling-laws was chosen to contain both the Protospace and full-sized model non-dimensional values, as presented in Table 5.4. Note that the liquid-solid contact angle lower limit allowed by the software was 6° and thus does not contain the 0° value for kerosene. It was, however, found that (see next section) the key importance of the contact angle lies in the initial meniscus, that is, whether the contact angle is 90° or not. This is because the We numbers are high, while a 90° contact angle results in the absence of Rayleigh–Taylor instability and therefore there is no violent slosh. Note also that in Table 5.4 the density ratio and Fr number ranges were selected to be broad for industrial relevance. The Re and We number ranges then followed from the above by allowing the range in viscosity (μ) and surface tension (γ) to vary between water and kerosene.

Table 5.3: Protospace vs full aircraft non-dimensional properties

	Actual Protospace	Froude-scaled Protospace	Aircraft
θ	60°	0	0
$\bar{\rho}$	1.21×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}
Re	459×10^3	13.3×10^3	148×10^3
We	27.8×10^3	13.4×10^3	337×10^3
Fr	5.86	2.81	2.81

Table 5.4: Non-dimensional property parameter space

Parameter	Property Range
$\theta \in [6^\circ, 90^\circ]$	—
$Re \in [1.33 \times 10^4, 4.59 \times 10^5]$	$\therefore \mu \in [9.772 \times 10^{-4}, 14.1 \times 10^{-3}] Pa.s$
$\bar{\rho} \in [6.04 \times 10^{-4}, 3.02 \times 10^{-3}]$	$\therefore \rho \in [399, 2.0 \times 10^3] kg.m^{-3}$
$We \in [1.34 \times 10^4, 2.78 \times 10^4]$	$\therefore \gamma \in [0.03, 0.073] N.m^{-1}$
$Fr \in [1.68, 8.8]$	$\therefore f \in [2.01, 10.5] Hz$

5.5 Non-Dimensional Study Quantitative Analysis

The influence on the fluid's reaction due to the scaling across the parameter space is shown in Figure 5.2, comparing the fluid reaction at impact of the Protospace experiment at $n = 0.6$, where n is the number of oscillations. The variation of fluid reactions accounts for the varying sloshing fluid dissipation energy, surface work and vertical sloshing force across the parameter space.

Figure 5.1: Influence of scaling on fluid reaction at $n = 0.6$ (a) Protospace Compartment; (b) $\theta = 1.57$

Figure 5.2: Influence of scaling on fluid reaction at $n = 0.6$ (a & b) θ scaling; (c & d) Re scaling; (e & f) $\bar{\rho}$ scaling; (g & h) We scaling; (i & j) Fr scaling

Figures 5.3 to 5.7 present comparative ranges for the influence of fluid properties on the normalised sloshing fluid dissipation energy ($\|E_{Disp}\|$), surface work ($\|W_s\|$) and vertical sloshing force ($\|F_y\|$). The influence range of each non-dimensional number on the aforementioned quantities is presented via the shaded region.

Figure 5.3: Influence of θ scaling on slosh-induced damping, work, and loads (a) $\|E_{Disp}\|$; (b) $\|W_s\|$; (c) $\|F_y\|$

Figure 5.4: Influence of Re scaling on slosh-induced damping, work, and loads (a) $\|E_{Disp}\|$; (b) $\|W_s\|$; (c) $\|F_y\|$

Figure 5.5: Influence of $\bar{\rho}$ scaling on slosh-induced damping, work, and loads (a) $\|E_{Disp}\|$; (b) $\|W_s\|$; (c) $\|F_y\|$

Figure 5.6: Influence of We scaling on slosh-induced damping, work, and loads (a) $\|E_{Disp}\|$; (b) $\|W_s\|$; (c) $\|F_y\|$

Figure 5.7: Influence of Fr scaling on slosh-induced damping, work, and loads (a) $\|E_{Disp}\|$; (b) $\|W_s\|$; (c) $\|F_y\|$

Table 5.5: RMS variation due to fluid property scaling relative to the actual Protospace (%)

	$\ E_{Disp}\ $	$\ W_s\ $	$\ F_y\ $
θ	36.05	11.34	14.32
Re	9.44	5.27	9.04
$\bar{\rho}$	12.53	6.25	12.20
We	20.86	9.09	18.11
Fr	106.38	88.90	15.77
$\theta = 90^\circ$	86.35	37.55	14.28

Table 5.5 lists the percentage root-mean-square difference due to the scaling of each non-dimensional property as compared to the actual Protospace values. The analysis reveals the relatively small influence for the scaling of θ , Re , $\bar{\rho}$ and We on $\|W_s\|$ where $RMSE < 14\%$. Additionally, the scaling of Re and $\bar{\rho}$ provide a relatively small influence on $\|E_{Disp}\|$ where $RMSE < 13\%$. θ and We have a significant influence on the $\|E_{Disp}\|$ where the $RMSE$ is approximately 36% and 21% respectively. This highlights the influence of surface tension and the initial free surface definition on the energy dissipation of the system. The scaling of the contact angle of 90° results in no liquid-gas surface instability (Rayleigh–Taylor) and hence no slosh damping (note that the reported 86.35% variation is due to numerically induced free-surface instability which occurs late in the analysis). At this point in the scaling analysis, the choice of Froude scaling (as opposed to Re etc.) is vindicated (and consistent with industrial practice), as all other fluid properties are shown to have a relatively small effect. This was further also demonstrated by a recent experimental campaign [24].

Note that although one would expect the Fr number to be important in an inertial system under gravity, what is certainly new is the direct relationship between the Fr number and slosh induced damping. What may also be counter intuitive, is the weak relationship between fluid viscosity and slosh induced damping.

Due to the selected scaling parameter spaces (Table 5.4) the scaling of fluid properties towards the kerosene properties results in a general increase in the SDOF $\|E_{Disp}\|$ and $\|W_s\|$. This is not necessarily true for the slosh loads predicted by $\|F_y\|$. The scaling of Fr around the protospace value results in the Protospace SDOF being the mean value for $\|E_{Disp}\|$ and $\|W_s\|$

Finally the effect that Froude scaling (via changing the excitation frequency) has on the system system is considered, with the results shown in Figure 5.7. Interestingly, for

the Froude number range tested, the major effect is on slosh damping as shown, that is, 106.38%. This concludes the important new insight that slosh-induced dissipation is highly sensitive to the Froude number.

Work relating to gravity waves within tanks has established the importance of Froude and Weber numbers on the fluid velocity due to the tank depth [66] which is dependent on Froude number for shallow tanks and Weber number for deep tanks. The selection of an intermediate tank depth in this work may negate the importance of these numbers to slosh induced dissipation.

5.6 Closure

The chapter has presented the first-ever finite volume method (FVM) volume of fluid (VOF) computational fluid dynamics (CFD) based non-dimensional analysis which characterises violent slosh-induced energy dissipation of a tank under vertical excitation. This is in the absence of significant phase change. The use of rigorously validated CFD for this purpose is essential as doing so via experimental means is not possible due to limitations in available liquids. The work resulted in several new insights which are deemed of significant value to the field liquid slosh modelling and liquid impact dynamics. These key contributions are summarised next.

Next, a non-dimensional analysis was detailed. The specific emphasis was on developing a functional relationship between energy dissipation and fluid physics. The latter was characterised by Reynolds number, Weber number, contact angle, gas-liquid density ratio and Froude number. The validated CFD software was then used to estimate the influence of each of these non-dimensional numbers on slosh-induced energy dissipation. As would be expected, Rayleigh-Taylor instability was found to be key to inducing liquid impact due to purely vertical excitation. Hence, an appropriate contact angle is a key to inducing violent vertical slosh-induced energy dissipation. The influences for the scaling of θ , Re , $\bar{\rho}$, We and Fr were then quantified in terms of their influence on slosh-induced energy dissipation. Due to the large impact of the Froude number scaling, the Froude number was concluded to be the most important non-dimensional number in characterising slosh-induced damping.

Chapter 6

CFD-Based Non-Dimensional Characterisation of Energy Dissipation due to Vertical Slosh

6.1 Introduction

The Chapter to follow aims to quantify slosh-induced energy vs. the key fluid physics non-dimensional numbers. Constant amplitude of excitation is employed to simplify the analysis. Therefore, the slosh-induced energy dissipation is expressed in terms of Froude number, and liquid-gas density ratio and contact angle via CFD-generated curve fits. Finally, it is demonstrated how the newly fitted non-dimensional scaling laws may be used with ease to estimate the slosh-induced damping of both ideally scaled experiments and full-scale (aircraft size) tanks.

6.2 Dissipated Energy Scaling Laws

6.2.1 Total Dissipated Energy Scaling Laws

As stated above, constant amplitude excitation is considered which implies setting $\xi = 0$. The resulting displacement and acceleration functions are:

$$y(t) = -y_0 \cos(\omega t) \tag{6.1}$$

$$\ddot{y}(t) = \omega^2 y_0 \cos(\omega t) \tag{6.2}$$

Setting $\xi = 0$ simplifies the calculation of slosh-induced dissipation to:

$$E_{Disp} \approx \int_0^t F_y u_{dy} dt \quad (6.3)$$

The % change in computed slosh-induced dissipation energy due to a change in a non-dimensional parameter (from the Protospace value $E_{Disp}(\text{Protospace})$) is expressed as:

$$||\Delta E_{Disp}|| = \frac{E_{Disp} - E_{Disp}(\text{Protospace})}{|E_{Disp}(\text{Protospace})|} \quad (6.4)$$

The validated CFD model was next employed to compute Equation (6.4) as a function of a specific dimensionless number. This was done by varying slosh parameters (excitation frequency and liquid properties) such that only the specific dimensionless number being scaled was effected. The resulting data points together with the trend lines are depicted in Figure 6.1. Also delineated on the figures are the properties for the Protospace (black line) and full aircraft scale tank (violet line). While no clear statistical trend was found for We and Re for the parameter space considered (thus they are not shown), the following cubic trend for θ was found to be around 60° :

$$||\Delta E_{Disp}||(\theta) = 21.44\theta^3 - 2987.35\theta^2 + 383.99\theta - 161.7 \quad (6.5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.82$$

Here, r^2 is the weighted sum of the squares of the difference between the fitted curve and the data such that $r^2 \in [0, 1]$ with $r^2 = 1$ being a perfect fit. Outliers to this trend occur due to lack of Rayleigh-Taylor instability for $\theta = 90^\circ$, which leads to $P_{Disp} \rightarrow 0$, while an enlarged meniscus results as $\theta \rightarrow 0$ (to be investigated in future work).

A very well-defined trend can, however, be found for the scaling of $\bar{\rho}$ as:

$$||\Delta E_{Disp}||(\bar{\rho}) = -0.54\bar{\rho}^{-0.802} + 117.39 \quad (6.6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.98$$

Similarly, a very well-defined trend is visible for the effect of the Froude number on slosh-induced dissipation. The resulting trend line reads:

$$||\Delta E_{Dis}||(Fr) = -2.46Fr^2 - 4.67Fr + 108.9 \quad (6.7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.98$$

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6.1: Change in dissipated energy due to scaling of non-dimensional properties (a) Liquid-solid contact angle $[\theta]$; (b) Density ratio $[\bar{\rho}]$; (c) Froude number $[Fr]$

Equation (6.7) is quadratic in nature. This relationship between slosh-induced dissipation and Fr number is a novel finding from this study. Note that clear trend lines for $\bar{\rho}$ and Fr were also reported in the experimental work by Calderon-Sancheza et al. [24], thus further pointing to the efficacy of the CFD model. Note that in the latter cited work, the set-up was such that the quadratic relationship in (6.7) was not clear.

Note also that the difference in dissipated energy between the Protospace experiment Fr number and that of the actual aircraft (or indeed ideal experiment) is by far the most significant of all quantities. This points to the value of the derived scaling law to estimate the expected slosh-induced damping for the full-scale aircraft tank. This is dealt with in the next section.

From the above, it is evident that ΔE_{Disp} scales near-linearly with ρ (due to Equation (6.6)) and with v^2 (due to Equation (6.7)). The latter is a result of the maximum tank velocity $v \propto \omega$ due to = Equation (5.4). From this, it is postulated that it is possible to express dissipated energy as a linear function of tank kinetic energy:

$$E_{Disp} \propto \rho v^2 \tag{6.8}$$

for the violent slosh under consideration.

6.2.2 Dissipated Energy Scaling Laws per Oscillation

We digress briefly to investigate the difference in fitted scaling curves for each of the three cycles of oscillation. This is to confirm that scaling laws obtained per cycle are consistent with experimental observation that the slosh damping which occurs over the first two to three cycles of oscillation is representative of the energy dissipation potential. The resulting curves are shown in Figure 6.2, where similar r^2 correlations encountered previously were found in most cases (see equations to follow). Apart from the θ curves, there is a reasonable correlation between the curve fits obtained for the three cycles, with the Fr number curve faring the best. The θ correlation is of less concern due to significantly lower influence on slosh-induced damping, while Fr is the most important.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6.2: Change in dissipated energy due to scaling of non-dimensional properties for each oscillation n (b) Density ratio $[\bar{\rho}]$; (c) Froude number $[Fr]$

Cubic trends for the scaling of θ are found such that:

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=1}||(\theta) &= 385.58\theta^3 - 1083.33\theta^2 + 958.56\theta - 289.1 \\ r^2 &= 0.80 \end{aligned} \quad (6.9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=2}||(\theta) &= 673.36\theta^3 - 2078.01\theta^2 + 2057.49\theta - 647.4 \\ r^2 &= 0.66 \end{aligned} \quad (6.10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=3}||(\theta) &= -436.37\theta^3 + 1438\theta^2 + 146.68\theta - 125.8 \\ r^2 &= 0.50 \end{aligned} \quad (6.11)$$

Better correlations were found for mass ratio:

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=1}||(\bar{\rho}) &= -145.9\bar{\rho}^{-0.7322} + 118.1 \\ r^2 &= 0.94 \end{aligned} \quad (6.12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=2}||(\bar{\rho}) &= -96.6\bar{\rho}^{-1.12} + 98.03 \\ r^2 &= 0.84 \end{aligned} \quad (6.13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=3}||(\bar{\rho}) &= -169.2\bar{\rho}^{-0.7495} + 130.9 \\ r^2 &= 0.91 \end{aligned} \quad (6.14)$$

The best trend was found throughout for Fr number with all trend lines being quadratic in nature:

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=1}||(Fr) &= -2.646Fr^2 - 3.594Fr + 109.9 \\ r^2 &= 0.99 \end{aligned} \quad (6.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=2}||(Fr) &= -3.095Fr^2 + 1.707Fr + 101 \\ r^2 &= 0.98 \end{aligned} \quad (6.16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=3}||(Fr) &= -1.448Fr^2 - 14.33Fr + 121.9 \\ r^2 &= 0.96 \end{aligned} \quad (6.17)$$

6.2.3 Dissipated Energy Geometric Scaling Law

Prior to employing the scaling laws to estimate the slosh-induced dissipation of the full scale tank, the geometric scaling law has to be created. This is because the excitation velocity is affected directly by geometric scaling, as per Table 2.1. Utilising the undamped excitation signal as defined by Equations (6.1) and (6.2) and a scaled parameter space $\lambda \in [1, 5]$, a geometric scaling law may be fitted for the first three oscillations of the system.

Figure 6.3: Dissipated energy $\|\Delta E_{Disp}\|$ vs geometric scale $[\lambda]$

Figure 6.3 depicts the discrete $\|\Delta E_{Disp}\|$ values for individual geometric scales (λ) as well as the resulting trend line. Also delineated on the figures are the properties for the Protospace (black line) and full aircraft (green line). A cubic trend is found for the scaling of λ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Delta E_{Disp}\|(\lambda) &= -52.31\lambda^3 - 220.8\lambda^2 + 278.3\lambda \\ r^2 &= 0.999 \end{aligned} \tag{6.18}$$

with a high correlation.

Figure 6.4: Change in dissipated energy due to scaling of geometry (λ) for each oscillation n

As completed previously, the difference in fitted scaling curves for each of the three cycles of oscillation is investigated. The resulting curves are shown in Figure 6.4, while similar r^2 correlations to those previously were found as per the equations to follow.

Trends for the scaling of λ number with all trend lines being cubic in nature:

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=1}||(\lambda) &= -51.39\lambda^3 - 270.6\lambda^2 + 316.3\lambda \\ r^2 &= 0.999 \end{aligned} \quad (6.19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=2}||(\lambda) &= -59.04\lambda^3 + -168.1\lambda^2 + 250\lambda \\ r^2 &= 0.996 \end{aligned} \quad (6.20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} ||E_{Disp}^{n=3}||(\lambda) &= -61.68\lambda^3 + -57.49\lambda^2 + 71.52\lambda \\ r^2 &= 0.986 \end{aligned} \quad (6.21)$$

6.3 Scaling-Laws Validation

It can be recalled that the scaling between the full aircraft model and the Protospace experiment employed an approximate Froude scaling due to being limited by experimental design and fluid availability (section 2.2.1). While the geometric scaling can be completed

independently of the properties of the fluid (due to it being a fundamental unit), the fluid physics scaling requires a more complex procedure whereby the changes in the fluid non-dimensional parameters are to be assessed simultaneously. Noting that well correlated scaling laws were derived above for the scaling of both Fr and $\bar{\rho}$, it is possible to develop a response surface for $||\Delta E_{Disp}||$.

6.3.1 Kriging Response Surface

The interpolation technique selected for the generation of the $||\Delta E_{Disp}||$ response surface is that of Kriging interpolation or Gaussian process regression. Kriging provides an interpolation method which has been proved accurate in the modelling of complex non-linear systems [67, 8, 13]. The interpolation technique provides a linear unbiased prediction and returns the exact value of training points, unlike alternative interpolation methods which employ a smoothing function [68].

The interpolation method employs an optimised regression analysis between unknown and trained data points, where a set of covariance values [69] allows for the weighting of surrounding data points. The predicted height of the response surface (\mathbf{y}) at a specified query point (\mathbf{x}) can be estimated through the sum of a regression model $F(\mathbf{x})$ and a stochastic Gaussian process $z(\mathbf{x})$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} y(\mathbf{x}) &= F(\mathbf{x}) + z(\mathbf{x}) \\ &= \beta_i f_i(\mathbf{x}) + z(\mathbf{x}) \end{aligned} \tag{6.22}$$

where F provides global approximations by means of a linear combination of regression functions $f_i(\mathbf{x})$ and a corresponding unknown weighting regression parameter, β_i .

Third-order regression polynomials were employed for this work as they were found to provide an appropriate model for the non-dimensional parameter space within this work. z allows local derivations to be accounted for and is assumed to have a mean of zero ($\bar{Z}(\mathbf{x})$). The covariance between two points i and j can be calculated such that

$$C_{ij} = E [z(\mathbf{x}_i), z(\mathbf{x}_j)] = \sigma^2 R(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) \tag{6.23}$$

E is the expected value, σ^2 is the variance of y correlation function, R is the a correlation function and θ is an anisotropic weights for the components of x respectively. While multiple options exist for the spatial correlation function, the smooth and continuous nature of the derived scaling laws identifies the spline correlation model as suitable for the scaling laws over the parameter space.

Given n samples such that $y_i = y(\mathbf{x}_i)$, the Kriging predictor (\hat{y}) can be defined as a linear combination of y_i with weights λ_i and an associated error (ϵ_i) such that

$$\hat{y}(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda_i y_i \quad (6.24)$$

$$\epsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \hat{y}(\mathbf{x}) - y(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda_i z(\mathbf{x}_i) - z(\mathbf{x}) + \beta_k [\lambda_i f_k(\mathbf{x}_i) - f_k(\mathbf{x})] \quad (6.25)$$

Solving for λ_i in order to minimise ϵ and such that $\lambda_i f_k(\mathbf{x}_i) - f_k(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ to ensure an unbiased interpolation process. The variance within this system may be minimised by means of Lagrange multipliers, leading to the final equations, which may be solved by matrix inversion,

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ij} \lambda_i &= c_i \\ \therefore \mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\lambda} + \mathbf{F}\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} &= \mathbf{c} \end{aligned} \quad (6.26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_i f_k(\mathbf{x}_i) &= f_k(\mathbf{x}) \\ \therefore \mathbf{F}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda} &= \mathbf{f} \end{aligned} \quad (6.27)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{F}^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\lambda} \\ \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c} \\ \mathbf{f} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.28)$$

Within this thesis the Kriging response surface was created via the MATLAB Kriging toolbox [70].

6.3.2 Scaling-Laws Application

The developed scaling laws will now be applied to estimate the slosh-induced damping for the full-scale tank. This will then be compared to actual CFD simulations to assess the applicability of the scaling laws.

As noted previously, first a 3D response surface (via Kriging) was created that correlates change in dissipated energy for both Fr and $\bar{\rho}$ (Figure 6.5). This was employed to obtain $||\delta E_{Disp}||$ for both Fr and ideally scaled experiments (complete fluid physics similarity with the aircraft tank). The latter are respectively denoted by Fr^\dagger and Fr^* with the corresponding dimensionless properties listed in Table 6.1 and with slosh loads shown in Figure 6.6. Next, a geometric scaling is applied based on the dimensionless properties of the ideally scaled experiment Fr^* . Note that the above two-step process

could also have been done via fitting a higher dimensional response surface (Fr , $\bar{\rho}$ and λ).

Table 6.1: Fluid properties due to Froude scaling (Nomenclature for scaling methods as defined above.)

	<i>Protospace</i> (Water)	<i>Protospace</i> [†] (Cold Kerosene)	<i>Protospace</i> [*] (Ideal)	<i>Aircraft</i> (Cold Kerosene)
$\bar{\rho}$	1.21×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}	1.39×10^{-3}
Re	459×10^3	13.3×10^3	149×10^3	149×10^3
We	27.8×10^3	13.4×10^3	337×10^3	337×10^3
Fr	5.86	2.81	2.81	2.81

Figure 6.5: Response surface of $||\Delta E_{Disp}||$ as a function of $\bar{\rho}$ and Fr

Figure 6.6: Force response for the various scaling of the Protospace experiment where \dagger indicates cold kerosene experiment and $*$ indicates ideal fluid

Table 6.2: Dissipated energy for SDOF system

	<i>Protospace</i>	<i>Protospace</i> \dagger	<i>Protospace</i> $*$	<i>Aircraft</i>
$E_{Disp}(\text{CFD}) [W]$	-46.75	-6.28	-6.64	-714.63
$E_{Disp}(\text{Scaling Laws}) [W]$	-46.75	-6.06	-6.06	-624.2
$\epsilon [\%]$	—	3.52	8.73	12.65

The scaling law derived dissipation value may be compared to that obtained via CFD for the different cases in Table 6.2. As shown, scaling from Protospace to Froude-scaled results in an error of 3.52%, and 8.73% for the ideally scaled experiment. Finally, the scaling laws predict a dissipated value which is 12.65% from the CFD-computed value for the full size aircraft tank. This is deemed a valuable result and shows clear value of the proposed new CFD-based scaling law philosophy. Note that a difference in scaling and CFD results was expected as the effect of Re and We numbers were not considered in the aforementioned.

6.4 Closure

The validated CFD was employed to characterise the change in slosh-induced dissipation as a function of the most important non-dimensional numbers for the case of constant amplitude oscillatory tank excitation. Clear correlations (scaling laws) were found for the

liquid-gas density ratio, Froude number and geometric scaling. The latter scaling laws are linear, quadratic, and cubic, respectively, which is deemed a significant new finding. Thereafter, the chapter demonstrates the application of the developed scaling laws for Froude number, density ratio and geometric scaling to estimate slosh-induced energy dissipation for an ideally scaled experiment and thereafter the full-scale aircraft. Accuracies of 91% and 87% were respectively achieved when compared to the CFD computed value.

Chapter 7

A Novel CFD-Based Reduced-Order Pressure Distribution Model

7.1 Introduction

A current widely employed procedure for accounting for slosh loads in the FAM is the frozen-mass-model (FMM). Complementary pressure distributions in the tank are then predicted via a quasi-static approach (Figure 7.1), which for violent vertical slosh is almost completely ineffective (as will be shown below). The SLOWD project is therefore working to replace the FMM slosh loads ROM with a novel mechanical model which offers greater accuracy in terms of dynamic slosh load. The resulting predicted load is then to be complemented by a consistent pressure distribution (such that the total load is similar to the new slosh ROM). The development of a novel pressure distribution ROM for this purpose constitutes the final contribution of this work.

7.2 Current Quasi-static Pressure Distribution ROM

A currently widely used model to predict slosh loads in the FAM is the FMM:

$$\mathbf{F}_{slosh} = m_l \mathbf{a}_{tank} \quad (7.1)$$

where m_l and \mathbf{a}_{tank} are the liquid mass within the tank and tank accelerations respectively.

Employing similar assumptions, industry then computes the resulting pressure distribution by assuming that the liquid has reached a steady-state response where the free surface is perpendicular to the net-acceleration vector of the tank for each time step. This allows the pressure (p_1) at any point on the wetted tank wall to be computed as

$$p_1 = p_0 + \rho_l \mathbf{h}_l \cdot \mathbf{a}_{tank} \quad (7.2)$$

where p_0 is the gas pressure within the tank, ρ_l is the liquid density and \mathbf{h}_l is the liquid height parallel to the tank acceleration (\mathbf{a}_{tank}), as per Figure 7.1.

Figure 7.1: Quasistatic fuel pressure distribution model

Considering the Protospace tank undergoing both lateral excitation (\mathbf{a}) and rotational kinetics ($\boldsymbol{\omega}_b, \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b$) about the empty tank geometric centre b , the tank acceleration at point p_1 is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{a}_{tank} = \mathbf{a} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b \times \mathbf{r} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{r}) \quad (7.3)$$

where \mathbf{r} is defined as the vector between the point b and p_1 . An algorithm outlining finding both the liquid interface position as well as wall static pressure is given by Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Quasi-static pressure distribution loads ROM (Single time-step)

Data: Tank Geometry, Fill-level (η_0), Tank Pressurisation (p_0), Fuel Density (ρ_l), Tank Acceleration History (\mathbf{a}_{tank}), Tolerance (ϵ)

Result: Pressure Load for Fuel due to acceleration at tank corners n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k
($p_{n_1}, p_{n_2}, \dots, p_{n_k}$)

$V_{tank} \leftarrow$ total tank volume ;

Liquid surface initialised on any tank corner ;

$c_y \leftarrow$ determine plane constant for \mathbf{a}_{tank} direction;

$V_{Target} \leftarrow V_{tank}\eta_0$;

$V_{liquid} \leftarrow$ total fluid volume bound by tank and liquid surface;

while $\epsilon > |V_{target} - V_{liquid}|$ **do**

if $V_{liquid} < V_{Target}$ **then**

$c_y \leftarrow$ increase c_y

else

$c_y \leftarrow$ decrease c_y

end

Re-initialised liquid surface.;

$V_{liquid} \leftarrow$ total fluid volume bound by tank and liquid surface;

end

for $i = 1:k$ **do**

$\mathbf{h}_l \leftarrow$ height to liquid surface from point on tank wall i;

if $\mathbf{h}_l \cdot \mathbf{a}_{tank}$ **then**

$p_i = p_0 + \rho_l \mathbf{h}_l \cdot \mathbf{a}_{tank}$

else

$p_i \leftarrow p_0$

end

end

Figure 7.2 compares the liquid interface as predicted via high-fidelity CFD and the quasi-static pressure distribution model. The comparison highlights the error in both the free-surface location (and therefore pressure distribution) and fluid centre of gravity resulting from the use of the quasi-static method for modelling vertical slosh. Note also that no liquid impact is observed (as would be expected) and hence no slosh-induced dissipation results. An additional weakness of the quasi-static method is the discontinuity in fluid motion, especially where the $\mathbf{a}_{tank} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_y$ changes sign. This results in the fluid mass jumping from the tank roof to the tank base.

Figure 7.2: High-fidelity CFD fluid response vs quasi-static pressure ROM fluid response (a-d) High-fidelity CFD; (e-h) Quasi-static pressure ROM

7.3 A Dynamic Pressure Distribution ROM

The drive for a dynamic pressure distribution ROM requires the incorporation of non-linear violent fluid motion within the ROM between individual time steps, in order to capture vertical slosh. At the same time, it has to be mass and momentum conservative in order not to lose or gain either over thousands of time-steps. As discussed previously, the FVM-VOF method provides a non-linear mass and momentum conservative solution procedure which is able to predict the free-surface location due to a given excitation accurately. The employment of a coarse mesh FVM-VOF simulation provides reduced computational cost while providing the aforementioned conservation properties. While being fully non-linear, the FVM-VOF CPU total time costing can be expressed as

$$t_{CPU} \approx \frac{N_n \Delta T_{CPU}^* t_{sim}}{\Delta t} \quad (7.4)$$

where N_n is the number mesh of nodes, ΔT_{CPU}^* is a CPU specific unit cost and Δt presents the average time step size of the simulation of length t_{sim} . Where the number of CPUs per a simulation is selected to allow ΔT_{CPU}^* to remain constant and therefore assumes an optimal core count for the selected FVM-VOF simulation. Note that the number of processors is not included in (7.4) as it will be included in terms of wall-clock time below. All available CPUs will be employed for coarse mesh simulations by being able to spawn more concurrent calculations. Therefore

$$t_{CPU} \propto \frac{N_n}{\Delta t} \quad (7.5)$$

Given a specific tank geometry and isotropic mesh (as is employed in this work), (7.5) may be expressed in terms of the average mesh spacing by noting that:

$$N_n \propto \frac{1}{\Delta x}^{Dim} \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t \propto \Delta x \quad (7.6)$$

This yields

$$t_{CPU} \propto \frac{1}{\Delta x}^{Dim+1} \quad (7.7)$$

which implies that the calculation cost is indirectly proportional to the mesh spacing to the power 3 and 4 in 2D and 3D respectively. When considering the effect of mesh spacing on wall-clock time, we will assume linear parallel speed-up down to 10,000 elements per core. In this case Equation (7.7) becomes:

$$t_{wall-clock} \propto \frac{10,000}{\Delta x} \quad (7.8)$$

The significantly lower speed-up in wall-clock time between coarse and fine mesh simulations is due to far more cores being useable in the case of the latter.

Note that the above computational speed advantage comes at the cost of accuracy (due to the larger mesh element sizes). To address this in this work, the target loads from the new pressure distribution ROM (under development within SLOWD) will be leveraged by adjusting liquid properties at each target slosh load time-step so as to minimise the difference between the pressure distribution ROM-produced and target slosh loads. The liquid properties chosen for this purpose were viscosity and surface tension. Neither of these affects the Fr number, which the dimensionless scaling analysis demonstrated as key. The rationale for the fluid viscosity was that coarse meshes cannot account for turbulence via LES, while surface tension is known to have an effect on the slosh loads.

7.4 Reduced-Order Model Algorithm

A generalised algorithm for the ROM is presented in Appendix A.2. In summary, the ROM takes as input the tank geometry, excitation history, fill level, liquid properties and target slosh load force history. A coarse mesh is then generated and the CFD simulation commenced. As part of this, a 2D response surface is created for the liquid viscosity and surface tension. As such, each time-step is re-run using different liquid viscosity and surface tension values (as defined by the parameter space) to minimise the difference between the computed and target slosh load. For this, an optimisation algorithm was required.

In the interest of efficiency due to the high expense of data points when using CFD, gradient type optimisation methods are often employed. The steepest descent method [71] is a prime example. In the context of this work, however, the slosh load data are particularly noisy due to the liquid impact (as is evident from Figures 5.7 and 8.1), which results in poor performing optimisation. In this work, a pragmatic “first attempt” solution to this was to create a “smooth” response surface from noisy data. This involved creating a smooth cubic polynomial curve fit using an over-defined data set. ELEMENTAL[®] was again used for the above as it allows restarting a time-step with altered material properties as well as containing least squares and steepest descent libraries.

For the purpose of creating the response surface data set at each force history time step, the liquid viscosity and surface tension were allowed to vary by an order of magnitude (larger was found to effect code stability). A least squares method was then employed for the fit, which then offered exceptional performance from the steepest descent method. The least square cubic fitting requires a minimum of 8 training points. The largest

computational cost was generating enough CFD data points, which in this work was found to be 12 to balance speed and accuracy (efficiency). The 12 data points consisted of a 4×3 matrix, that is, 4 surface tension values and 3 viscosity values. This is as per Table 5.5. The slosh load is more sensitive to surface tension (We) than viscosity (Re). Note that due to the creation of a response surface, the global minimum could be found by restarting the steepest descent method from different initial conditions. Employing a smooth cubic polynomial curve fit provides at least two stationary points. Therefore three restarts were employed to provide the possible locations for the global minima, and the minima was determined by means of comparing these points.

7.4.1 Least Squares Surface Fitting Procedure

As noted above, a smooth response surface was created from noisy data via a least-squares method [72]. For a given data set $Z_f(\mu, \gamma)$ containing more than 10 data points, a 3^{rd} order polynomial surface is fit:

$$S = a_0 + a_1\mu_i + a_2\gamma_i + a_3\mu_i^2 + a_4\mu_i\gamma_i + a_5\gamma_i^2 + a_6\mu_i^2\gamma_i + a_7\mu_i\gamma_i^2 + a_8\mu_i^3 + a_9\gamma_i^3 \quad (7.9)$$

The least squares equations for surface fitting may be derived such that it yields a symmetrical matrix (\mathbb{M}) and a vector \mathbf{b} allowing for the calculation of a_j from

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbb{M}^{-1}\mathbf{b} \quad (7.10)$$

The above approach is capable of being expanded to fit higher-order polynomials. In the case of the tailoring of the influence of liquid viscosity and surface tension scaling, the use of 3^{rd} order surfaces proved sufficiently accurate to capture the general trend (as demonstrated within Section 8.4).

7.4.2 Steepest Descent Method

The stationary points (maxima and minima) of a smooth surface may be calculated by means of gradient-type optimisation methods such as the steepest descent method [73]. As such, this method is employed for optimisation within the pressure distribution ROM. Employing the smooth continuous response surface calculated above ($S(x, y)$), the steepest descent vector at (x_0, y_0) is provided by $-\nabla S(x_0, y_0)$. Considering the function:

$$\varphi(t) = f(\mathbf{x}_0 + t\mathbf{u}) \quad (7.11)$$

where \mathbf{u} is a unit vector, $\frac{\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_0)}{\|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_0)\|}$ and $\mathbf{x}_0 = (x_0, y_0)$.

This converts the multi-variable surface optimisation into a single-variable minimisation problem, where $\varphi(t)$ is minimised. This minimisation is employed within an iterative method such that:

$$\min \varphi_k(t) = f(\mathbf{x}_k - t \frac{\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k)}{\|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k)\|}) \quad (7.12)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{x}_k - t_k \frac{\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k)}{\|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k)\|} \quad (7.13)$$

This iterative process is continued till $|f(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}) - f(\mathbf{x}_k)| < \epsilon$, where ϵ is a predefined convergence limit.

7.4.3 Optimisation Test Case

To evaluate the optimisation procedure in dealing with the noisy data as expected due to liquid impact (as discussed previously), a test case employing a 3rd order polynomial surface and random noise generator is employed. The discrete input data is generated at 12 equispaced data points by means of the following equation:

$$S_a(x, y) = 2y + 4x^2 - 4xy + 2y^2 - 200 + \text{rand} \in [-100, 100] \quad (7.14)$$

where S_a is the analytical surface selected for the test case. The least squares surface fitting method is then employed to fit a third order polynomial to the input data. The resulting least squares surface (S_{ls}) is

$$S_{ls}(x, y) = -209.29 - 5.41x - 5.64y + 4.26x^2 - 0.32xy + 2.04y^2 + 0.06x^2y - 0.007xy^2 - 0.009x^3 - 0.02y^3 \quad (7.15)$$

This surface is represented in Figure 7.3 against the input data points as calculated by Equation 7.14 where the magnitude of the random noise generator is shown as vectors.

Figure 7.3: Test case for least squares optimisation procedure

The steepest decent method is then utilised to calculate the minimum of the system from the starting position $\mathbf{x}_0 = [10, 10]$. Figure 7.4 depicts the steepest decent curve and the calculated local minima for the surfaces. Comparing the calculated value of the local minima ($\mathbf{x} = [0.88, 0.36]$) and the analytical value provides an error of $\epsilon = 2.54\%$ calculated by means of

$$\epsilon(x, y) = \frac{100(S_a(x, y) - S_{ls}(x, y))}{200} \quad (7.16)$$

Figure 7.4: Fitted least square surface, with gradient descent path and calculated global minimum

7.5 Closure

This chapter presents and critiques the current industrial quasi-static pressure distribution ROM. Thereafter, the dynamic pressure distribution ROM employing a tailored coarse mesh CFD solution procedure is described and an overview of the generalised algorithm is provided. Following this, the least squares optimisation procedure within the ROM is presented, including the least square response surface fitting procedure and steepest descent gradient type optimisation technique. The chapter concludes with the validation of the least squares optimisation procedure for a selected data set.

Chapter 8

Reduced-Order Pressure Distribution Model Test-Cases

8.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the developed algorithm for the novel pressure distribution ROM is assessed. The model is evaluated by means of application to a Protospace single compartment in both 2D and 3D. Its efficiency (cost and accuracy) is evaluated via comparison to detailed CFD calculations.

8.2 Pressure Distribution ROM Test Case Definition

The performance of the pressure distribution ROM is evaluated by again using the Protospace experimental campaign as utilised in Section 4.3. To simplify the analyses only the beam-tip compartment is considered, with a 50% fill-level, undergoing the selected Protospace experimental accelerations as derived for use within 4.3.

Table 8.1 presents the runs and the properties utilised within the evaluation to follow.

Table 8.1: Evaluation run types and properties

	High Fidelity	Untailored Low Fidelity	Low Fidelity ROM
Denoted as:	HF	UT	ROM
Mesh Spacing:	$\Delta x = 0.4mm$	$\Delta x \leq 0.02m$	$\Delta x \leq 0.02m$
Optimisation:	No	No	Yes

Figure 8.1: 2D and 3D high-fidelity ELEMENTAL[®] single compartment simulation results ($\Delta x_{HF} = 0.4mm$) (a) Vertical slosh loads; (b) Tank base pressure probe readings; (c) Tank roof pressure probe readings

Figure 8.2: 2D and 3D Probe location for ROM evaluation

Figure 8.3: 2D and 3D high-fidelity ELEMENTAL[®] single compartment predicted interface regimes ($\Delta x = 0.4mm$) - probe locations displayed as black dots within domain (a - c) 2D simulation; (d - f) 3D simulation cut through central x-z plane of tank

The high accuracies for both 2D and 3D ELEMENTAL[®] simulations in modelling slosh loads (Tables 4.1 and 4.2) allow the use of the experimental excitation profile and 2D and 3D simulations to provide the target loads for the ROM inputs. Figure 8.1 presents the target loads and pressure readings for the centre of the tank base and roof for the single compartment, as depicted by Figure 8.2.

Overall a good correlation is observed between 2D and 3D, with the largest differences being the highest impact events. Additionally, Figure 8.1 compares the *HF* and FMM vertical slosh loads (as per by Equation 7.1) for the given excitation profile. This highlights the FMM failure to capture peak loads. The comparison between the 2D and 3D pressure readings highlights that 2D CFD may either over or under predict peak pressures. It is worth noting the offset in the pressures seen between the 2D and 3D simulations within Figures 8.1b and 8.1c. Considering this, together with the inability of the FMM to model liquid impact pressures, it is recommended that 3D simulation be employed for tank structural component optimisation.

8.3 Performance Metrics for ROM operation

8.3.1 CPU ROM Costing Metrics

As a metric to evaluate the efficiency of the ROM, the speed-up factor Ω_{ROM} is used:

$$\Omega_{ROM} = \frac{t_{CPU}(HF)}{t_{CPU}(ROM)} \quad (8.1)$$

In the interest of completeness, the wall-clock time speed-up will also be given as follows:

$$\Omega_{ROM}^* = \frac{t_{wall-clock}(HF)}{t_{wall-clock}(ROM)} \quad (8.2)$$

To ensure consistency for the evaluation of the CPU costs, all simulations were completed on the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) Centre for High-Performance Computing (CHPC) Lengau Cluster as per Table 8.2 [74].

Table 8.2: CHPC Lengau system specifications

Parameter	Value
CPU	Intel [®] Xenon [®]
CPU Clock	2.6 GHz
Node Count	1368
Cores per Node	24
Memory	148.5 TB
Interconnect	FDR Infiniband Network

8.3.2 ROM Error Metrics

The use of the validated high-fidelity ELEMENTAL[®] stimulations as target loads allows evaluation of the ROM's performance in modelling the vertical slosh loads $F_y(ROM, t)$ and pressure probe readings for the centres of tank roof and base $p(ROM, t)$. In the interest of brevity, only two pressure probes are considered within this evaluation.

The error in vertical slosh load for the ROM can be expressed as:

$$\epsilon_F(ROM, t) = 100 \left(\frac{|F_y(ROM, t) - F_y(HF, t)|}{\max |F_y(HF, t)|} \right) \quad (8.3)$$

A similar error metric is employed for the pressure probe readings (ϵ_p).

8.4 Pressure Distribution ROM Evaluation

8.4.1 2D Pressure Distribution ROM

The pressure distribution ROM has been developed to provide both 2D and 3D reduced-order simulations. Using the 2D high-fidelity ELEMENTAL[®] simulation to provide the target loads for the ROM operation, and the measured tank accelerations from the Protopspace experiment as inputs, the ROM and untailed coarse simulation were evaluated over a range of different mesh spacings. The coarsest and finest mesh spacings considered for the ROM evaluation study are respectively $\Delta x = 0.02m$ and $\Delta x = 0.002m$. The errors in slosh load as a function of mesh spacing is given in Fig. 8.6. As shown, asymptotic convergence is achieved for circa $\Delta x \leq 5mm$.

Figure 8.4: 2D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$) fluid response vs high-fidelity (contour depicts free surface location) **(a-d)** high-fidelity tank pressure distribution; **(e-h)** ROM tank pressure distribution

Figure 8.5: Comparison of 2D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$), untailored and high-fidelity simulations (a) Vertical slosh loads; (b) Pressure for tank base probe; (c) Pressure for tank roof probe

For $\Delta x = 5mm$, Figure 8.4 compares the high-fidelity and ROM pressure distributions within the tank at various selected times, where the contour on the plots defines the CFD-predicted fluid free surface. The free surface location and pressure distribution may be compared to evaluate the ability of the ROM to represent the high-fidelity solution. Clear differences are seen at 0.085s where the 2D ROM under-predicts pressures while the liquid interface correlates slightly better. Figure 8.5 compares the high-fidelity CFD, ROM and untailed coarse mesh simulation results for the vertical slosh load and the two selected discrete pressure probes. As shown, the ROM material property tailoring provides a key improvement to the accuracies in peak force and pressure predictions. This is also evident from Table 8.3.

Table 8.3: Error analysis for selected 2D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x = 5mm$)

	ROM		UT	
	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]
ϵ_F	2.56	96.4	3.02	125.8
ϵ_E	3.20	5.81	7.40	11.27
ϵ_p	1.02	9.01	1.11	15.72

Comparing the maximum and L_2 Norm error metrics for the ROM and untailed coarse mesh simulation highlights the effect of the ROM on the maximum errors in all selected parameters. The ROM provides a limited improvement on the L_2 Norm of the error between the ROM and untailed simulation, except for slosh-induced energy dissipation where the ROM approximately halves the error of the untailed coarse simulation. A significant ROM improvement is also achieved in peak pressure and force predictions as compared to the untailed coarse mesh CFD.

Table 8.4 presents the speed-up factor for both the pressure ROM and the low-fidelity untailed simulations against the high-fidelity simulation. The untailed simulation and ROM provide wall-clock time speed-up factors of approximately 40.1 and 4.62 respectively. The ROM training therefore adds a factor 10 cost as would be expected (12 data points required per time-step). The use of the restart procedure results in an increased wall time due to the file handling required within the ROM operation. This was found to account for approximately 20% of the operation time.

Table 8.4: CPU performance characterisation for selected 2D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x = 5mm$)

	$t_{wall-clock}$ [h:m:s]	Ω [h:m:s]	Ω^*
HF	01 : 12 : 52	—	—
UT	00 : 01 : 49	723	40.1
ROM	00 : 17 : 36	48.5	4.62

Tables 8.6 & 8.5 and Figures 8.6 to 8.8 report on the speed-up factor and L_2 Norm of the error in vertical slosh loads for the full mesh sensitivity study. This highlights the level of convergence of both the ROM and the untailed coarse mesh simulation for $\|\epsilon_F\|_2$ for $\Delta x \leq 6.67mm$ and in maximum error for circa $\Delta x < 4mm$. As shown, the tailoring assists significantly in reducing the errors particularly on the courses meshes. This is at a significant cost, though. Overall, the ROM offers a wall-time speed-up of about 2 or more while the UT coarse mesh does one order of magnitude better for this slosh case.

Table 8.5: Force error and speed-up factor analysis for selected 2D pressure distribution for UT

Δx [mm]	$\ \epsilon_F\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon_F$ [%]	Ω	Ω^*
15	14.23	316.4	7226.8	98
10	8.11	208.3	2252.5	70.5
6.67	3.05	153.1	1284.8	58.3
5	3.02	125.8	723.3	40.1
4	2.62	95.6	445.6	29.1
3.33	2.43	72.2	260.5	20.8
2.5	2.91	76.6	137.4	13.8
2	2.82	76.6	74.8	9.89
1.6	2.01	70.9	49.5	4.58

Table 8.6: Force error and speed-up factor analysis for selected 2D pressure distribution for ROM

Δx [mm]	$\ \epsilon_F\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon_F$ [%]	Ω	Ω^*
15	6.01	196.8	485.4	7.32
10	3.02	178.2	151.3	6.36
6.67	2.73	145.1	86.3	5.55
5	2.56	96.4	48.5	4.62
4	2.55	76.3	30.4	3.25
3.33	2.28	72.4	17.7	2.94
2.5	2.42	71.8	9.03	2.16
2	2.59	69.1	4.30	1.62

Figure 8.6: $\|\epsilon_F\|_2$ for 2D pressure distribution ROM and untailored coarse simulations for various mesh resolutions

Figure 8.7: Ω for 2D pressure distribution ROM & UT simulations for various mesh resolutions

Figure 8.8: Ω^* for 2D pressure distribution ROM & UT simulations for various mesh resolutions

Next, an error comparison is done between the ROM and UT simulations where similar CPU costs result. For this purpose the $\Delta x(ROM) = 5mm$ and $\Delta x(UT) = 1.6mm$ meshes are employed respectively, which are with-in the asymptotic range. The resulting predicted slosh loads and pressure evolutions are shown in Fig 8.9.

Figure 8.9: Comparison of 2D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$), untailored ($\Delta x_{UT} = 1.6mm$) and high-fidelity simulations (a) Vertical slosh loads; (b) Pressure for tank base probe; (c) Pressure for tank roof probe

An error analysis for the selected meshes is provided in Table 8.7. Comparing the maximum and L_2 Norm error metrics for the ROM and untailed coarse mesh simulation highlights the influence of the mesh spacing on the modelling of slosh loads, pressure distributions and slosh-induced energy dissipation. In addition, the ROM is inferior in error for the same CPU cost and therefore still not competitive with the UT simulations. However, the UT coarse mesh offers orders of magnitude speed-ups as compared to the HF simulation and is therefore recommended as the ROM of choice.

Table 8.7: Error analysis for selected 2D pressure distribution ROM

	ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$)		UT ($\Delta x_{UT} = 1.6mm$)	
	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]
ϵ_F	2.56	96.4	2.01	70.92
ϵ_E	3.20	5.81	1.17	7.54
ϵ_p	1.02	9.01	0.49	6.23

8.4.2 3D Pressure Distribution ROM

To evaluate the effectiveness of the pressure distribution ROM for 3D modelling, a similar evaluation to that completed for the 2D evaluations is employed. Figure 8.10 compares the high-fidelity and ROM pressure distributions ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$) within the tank at various selected times, where the contour on the plots defines the CFD-predicted fluid free surface. The free surface location and pressure distribution may be compared to evaluate the ability of the ROM to represent the high-fidelity solution. When compared to Figure 8.4 it is clear that the 3D ROM provides an improved fluid free surface prediction when compared to the 2D ROM. Additionally, the 3D ROM is shown to provide an improved pressure prediction for the selected cross-section.

Figure 8.10: 3D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$) fluid response vs high-fidelity cut through central x-z plane of tank (contour depicts free surface location) (**a-d**) high-fidelity tank pressure distribution; (**e-h**) ROM tank pressure distribution

Figure 8.11 compares the high-fidelity CFD, ROM and untailed coarse mesh simulation results for the vertical slosh load and the two selected discrete pressure probes. As shown, the key improvement of the material property tailoring are improved peak force and pressure predictions.

Figure 8.11: Comparison of 3D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$), untailored and high-fidelity simulations (a) Vertical slosh loads; (b) Pressure for tank base probe; (c) Pressure for tank roof probe

Completing an error analysis for the selected mesh provides Table 8.8. Comparing the maximum and L_2 Norm error metrics for the ROM and untailed coarse mesh simulation highlights the effect of the ROM on the maximum errors in all selected parameters. The 3D ROM provides similar improvements to the error from the untailed simulation as the 2D ROM while in general being more accurate than the 2D variant. The improvement in maximum force error is now reduced by approximately 15% and the improvement in the maximum discrete pressure values is approximately 4%. The computational cost comparison is given in Table 8.9.

Table 8.8: Error analysis for selected 3D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$)

	ROM		UT	
	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]
ϵ_F	1.38	59.1	1.45	79.9
ϵ_E	3.07	4.14	4.26	7.49
ϵ_p	0.66	14.4	0.73	18.8

Note that the UT 3D simulation cost is similar to the HF 2D case. The untailed simulation and ROM provide wall-clock time speed-up factors of approximately 746 and 51.2 respectively, as presented in Table 8.9.

Table 8.9: CPU performance characterisation for selected 3D ROM ($\Delta x = 5mm$)

	$t_{wall-clock}$ [d:h:m:s]	Ω	Ω^*
HF	1 : 17 : 52 : 50	—	—
UT	0 : 00 : 03 : 27	4,833	746
ROM	0 : 00 : 53 : 42	324	51.2

A similar mesh independence study, as previously completed for the 2D is again completed for 3D. The coarsest and finest mesh spacings considered are respectively $\Delta x = 0.02m$ and $\Delta x = 0.0033m$. This provides Tables 8.10 & 8.11 and Figures 8.12 to 8.14.

Table 8.10: Force error and speed-up factor analysis for selected 3D pressure distribution for UT

Δx [mm]	$\ \epsilon_F\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon_F$ [%]	Ω	Ω^*
15	8.45	156	151,790	7,718
10	4.01	104	27,598	2,374
6.67	1.51	51.1	11,805	1,354
5	1.45	37.4	4,833	745
4	1.28	36.3	2,339	382
3.33	1.12	33.1	1,161	161

Table 8.11: Force error and speed-up factor analysis for selected 3D pressure distribution for ROM

Δx [mm]	$\ \epsilon_F\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon_F$ [%]	Ω	Ω^*
15	4.67	136	10,194	143.4
10	2.78	85.7	1853	107.9
6.67	1.48	42.2	792.9	77.2
5	1.39	35.4	324.4	51.2
4	1.24	32.8	159.5	29.1
3.33	1.22	28.2	78.81	16.2

Figure 8.12: $\|\epsilon_F\|_2$ for 3D pressure distribution ROM and untailored coarse simulations for various mesh resolutions

Figure 8.13: Ω for 3D pressure distribution ROM & UT simulations for various mesh resolutions

Figure 8.14: Ω^* for 3D pressure distribution ROM & UT simulations for various mesh resolutions

As in the 2D results, convergence of error for both the ROM and the untailed coarse mesh simulation is achieved for $\Delta x \leq 5mm$. From Tables 8.10 and 8.11, a comparison of the ROM and untailed coarse mesh simulation providing comparable wall-time speed-ups may be evaluated. As such with an Ω^* of approximately 50 the following mesh spacings are selected for this comparison: $\Delta x(ROM) = 5mm$ and $\Delta x(UT) = 3.125mm$.

Figure 8.15: Comparison of 2D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$), untailored ($\Delta x_{UT} = 3.125mm$) and high-fidelity simulations (a) Vertical slosh loads; (b) Pressure for tank base probe; (c) Pressure for tank roof probe

An error analysis for the selected meshes is provided in Table 8.12. Comparing the maximum and L_2 Norm error metrics for the ROM and untailed coarse mesh simulation highlights the influence of the mesh spacing on the modelling of slosh loads, pressure distributions and slosh-induced energy dissipation. The use of a reduced mesh spacing at the same computational cost of a coarse ROM mesh spacing provides improved performance across all metrics, with the maximum error in slosh-induced energy dissipation being the exception. Due the almost 3 orders of magnitude speed-ups achievable via the UT coarse mesh, it is deemed the ROM of choice.

Table 8.12: Error analysis for selected 3D pressure distribution ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$)

	ROM ($\Delta x_{ROM} = 5mm$)		UT ($\Delta x_{UT} = 3.125mm$)	
	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]	$\ \epsilon\ _2$ [%]	$\max \epsilon$ [%]
ϵ_F	1.38	59.1	0.89	37.00
ϵ_E	3.07	5.49	1.21	2.46
ϵ_p	0.66	14.4	0.42	5.03

8.5 Closure

This chapter detailed the evaluation of the reduced-order pressure distribution ROM as a tool for the prediction of tank pressure distributions due to the provided tank excitation, fill level and target load. The Protospace single compartment is employed for evaluation purposes.

The pressure distribution ROM and corresponding untailed coarse mesh simulations are evaluated, in both 2D and 3D, against the input high-fidelity simulations in respect of the vertical slosh loads, two discrete pressure probe readings, slosh-induced energy dissipation and the speed-up factor provided by the use of a coarse mesh. Both the ROM and UT coarse mesh simulations are shown to provide acceptable errors for industrial use, while offering speed-ups in total CPU time of an order of magnitude and 3 orders of magnitude respectively as compared to the high-fidelity CFD. The high tailoring cost and accuracy provided by the untailed coarse mesh favours the latter as use for the ROM.

Chapter 9

Conclusions and Recommendations

9.1 Summary

A novel yet practical CFD-based slosh-induced slosh loads estimation philosophy is presented, to provide an improvement to the current method employed routinely in the aerospace industry. The new philosophy leverages high-fidelity CFD together with non-dimensional analysis as a means of computing vertical slosh loads and slosh-induced energy dissipation. For this purpose, the rigorous validation of the chosen ELEMENTAL[®] FVM-VOF CFD software against the Protospace experimental campaign results is required.

It is thus demonstrated that a FVM-VOF based CFD scheme employing a weakly-compressible gas formulation is capable of computing violent slosh-induced energy dissipation with high accuracy (a 98% correlation with experimental vertical slosh loads is achieved). Additionally, it is shown that minimal 3D effects are present in the slosh loads calculations, thereby defending the use of 2D simulations within this study for the high-fidelity modelling of violent slosh in terms of a global loads analysis.

A non-dimensional analysis was detailed. The specific emphasis was on developing a functional relationship between energy dissipation and fluid physics. The latter was characterised by Reynolds number, Weber number, contact angle, gas-liquid density ratio and Froude number. The validated CFD software was then used to estimate the influence of each of these non-dimensional numbers on slosh-induced energy dissipation. As would be expected, Rayleigh–Taylor instability was found to be the key to inducing liquid impact due to purely vertical excitation. Hence, an appropriate contact angle is a key to inducing violent vertical slosh-induced energy dissipation. Compared to the Froude number, all other non-dimensional numbers were for the first time found to have a relatively small influence on slosh-induced energy dissipation. Hence, the Froude number was concluded to be the most important non-dimensional number in characterising violent slosh-induced

damping.

The validated CFD was then employed to characterise the change in slosh-induced dissipation as a function of selected non-dimensional numbers and geometric scaling for the case of a constant amplitude oscillatory tank excitation. Clear correlations (scaling laws) were found for both liquids–gas density ratio and Froude number. The latter scaling laws are linear and quadratic, respectively, which is deemed a significant new finding. From this, it was postulated for the first time that violent slosh-induced energy dissipation may be expressed as a linear function of tank kinetic energy. To emphasise the industrial importance of the aforementioned novel scaling laws, they were applied to estimate slosh-induced damping for both ideally scaled and full-scale slosh systems. The accuracies achieved when compared to high-fidelity CFD for ideal experiments (with exact fluid physics similarity to the full-scale Aircraft) and full-scale systems were 91% and 87% respectively.

The final novel contribution entailed a CFD-based pressure distribution ROM to replace the existing industrial standard ROM. The new ROM is composed of a tuned coarse mesh CFD. It takes as input tank geometry, liquid properties, target load and excitation history and then modifies liquid viscosity and surface tension coefficient to improve on accuracy. Both tailored and untailored coarse mesh CFD simulations demonstrated engineering precision, with the former being less sensitive to mesh spacing and in many cases more accurate, this, however, at CPU cost. In 2D, the ROM and untailored version were respectively an order and two orders of magnitude faster to run as compared to the high resolution CFD. The 3D coarse mesh untailored model was found to be particularly accurate in predicting vertical slosh loads ($\|\epsilon_F\|_2 = 3.02\%$ in 2D and 1.57% in 3D) and discrete pressures within a tank ($\|\epsilon_p\|_2 = 2.26\%$ in 2D and 0.49% in 3D) due to violent vertical slosh, with significant speed-ups in CPU cost as compared to the high-fidelity simulations.

9.2 Recommendations for Future Work

The proposed CFD-based loads estimation philosophy is suitable for use within the industry-standard full aircraft model. However, the following recommendations are made regarding future work:

- Lateral experimental slosh forces: Due to the experimental campaign design, the slosh loads perpendicular to the base of the tank were recorded. In future, lateral forces should also be measured.

- Fluid-structure interaction (FSI) CFD validation: The employment of a strongly coupled FSI system coupling ELEMENTAL[®] FVM-VOF simulation and non-linear CSM beam model allows the validation of both the slosh-induced loads and energy dissipation against the experimental Protospace campaign results. As part of the larger SLOWD project, the development of a framework capable of such simulations is under development. However, this framework does not form part of the scope of this study.
- Multi degree-of-freedom (MDOF) dimensional analysis: The scope of this study aimed to investigate the dissipation due to vertical excitation. For broader application, the philosophy would be required to operate with lateral and rotational excitations; therefore, the extension towards a MDOF dimensional analysis is required.
- The expansion of the non-dimensional analysis to incorporate fill level changes, allowing for the evaluation of the impact of non-dimensional numbers such as the ratio of free space distance above the fluid to amplitude of the tank excitation displacement on slosh energy dissipation.
- Increased non-dimensional property parameter space for scaling: As the industrial ROM is expected to operate efficiently across a vast range of operational conditions, the parameter space for the scaling of non-dimensional properties may require expansion.
- FSI scaling laws development: The use of an FSI simulation to complete the quantitative analysis of the non-dimensional property and geometric scaling of the system would allow for the derivation of scaling laws for $\Delta\xi_s$ directly for use with the industrial standard FAM.
- Pressure distribution ROM validation: Investigate methods of reducing the ROM tailoring cost via the use of AI.
- FAM implementation: The developed philosophy is to be formally implemented in industry to work seamlessly with the in-house FAM.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Derivations and Algorithms

A.1 Protospace Excitation Profile Derivation

Employing the rigid body dynamics formula for rotation and translation about a fixed axis,

$$\mathbf{a}_{p/A} = \mathbf{a}_{b/A} + \mathbf{a}_{p/b} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b}) + 2\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{u}_{p/b} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

For the case of the Protospace experimental campaign, $\mathbf{a}_{p/b} = 0$ and $\mathbf{u}_{p/b} = 0$ as the radius $\mathbf{r}_{p/b}$ is a rigid body. Therefore simplifying to

$$\mathbf{a}_{p/A} = \mathbf{a}_{b/A} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b} + \boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times (\boldsymbol{\omega}_b \times \mathbf{r}_{p/b}) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

expanding this formulation for the 3 DoF vector space.

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{px/A} \\ a_{py/A} \\ a_{pz/A} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{bx/A} \\ a_{by/A} \\ a_{bz/A} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\omega}_{bx} \\ \dot{\omega}_{by} \\ \dot{\omega}_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} r_{x/b} \\ r_{y/b} \\ r_{z/b} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{bx} \\ \omega_{by} \\ \omega_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \left(\begin{bmatrix} \omega_{bx} \\ \omega_{by} \\ \omega_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} r_{x/b} \\ r_{y/b} \\ r_{z/b} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Due to the need to incorporate gravity, $\mathbf{a}'_{b/A}$ is defined such that

$$\mathbf{a}'_{b/A} = \mathbf{a}_{b/A} + \mathbf{g}_A \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where \mathbf{g} provides the correction for the re-inclusion of gravity. Going forward, all acceleration terms will be written in the non-inertial basis (i.e. b) as this is the basis in which the accelerometer's measure.

$$\begin{bmatrix} a'_{px/A} \\ a'_{py/A} \\ a'_{pz/A} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a'_{bx/A} \\ a'_{by/A} \\ a'_{bz/A} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\omega}_{bx} \\ \dot{\omega}_{by} \\ \dot{\omega}_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} r_{x/b} \\ r_{y/b} \\ r_{y/b} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{bx} \\ \omega_{by} \\ \omega_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \left(\begin{bmatrix} \omega_{bx} \\ \omega_{by} \\ \omega_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} r_{x/b} \\ r_{y/b} \\ r_{z/b} \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The Protospace experimental set-up provides $\mathbf{a}_{b/A} = a_{bx/A}\hat{e}_x + a_{by/A}\hat{e}_y$ and $\mathbf{a}_{p/A} = a_{px/A}\hat{e}_x + a_{py/A}\hat{e}_y$, where $a_{p/A}$ and $a_{b/A}$ are the total perceived accelerations at point p and b due to the lateral and rotational kinetics of the system. In the case of the Protospace experiment, $a_{bz/A} = a_{pz/A} = 0$, $r_{p/b} = l\hat{e}_x$ and $\omega_{bx} = \omega_{by} = \dot{\omega}_{bx} = \dot{\omega}_{by} = 0$, therefore providing the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} a'_{px} \\ a'_{py} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a'_{bx} \\ a'_{by} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \dot{\omega}_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} l \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \omega_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \omega_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} l \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

This simplifies to

$$\begin{bmatrix} a'_{px/A} \\ a'_{py/A} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a'_{bx/A} \\ a'_{by/A} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \dot{\omega}_{bz}l \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \omega_{bz} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \omega_{bz}l \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{px/A} \\ a_{py/A} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{bx/A} \\ a_{by/A} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \dot{\omega}_{bz}l \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\omega_{bz}^2l \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

This system may then be separated into two unique equations by solving for each component:

$$a'_{px/A} = a'_{bx/A} - \omega_{bz}^2l \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$a'_{py/A} = a'_{by/A} + \dot{\omega}_{bz}l \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Solving for ω_{bz} and $\dot{\omega}_{bz}$ provides the following solutions:

$$\omega_{bz} = \sqrt{\frac{a'_{bx/A} - a'_{px/A}}{l}} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$\dot{\omega}_{bz} = \frac{a'_{py/A} - a'_{by/A}}{l} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

A.2 Dynamic Pressure Distribution ROM Algorithm

Algorithm 2: General algorithm for pressure distribution ROM

Data: Tank geometry & properties, fuel properties, acceleration history, global slosh forces, simulation length

Result: ELEMENTAL[®] pressure & visualisations outputs

$\Phi_\mu \leftarrow [\phi_\mu^0, \phi_\mu^1, \phi_\mu^2, \dots, \phi_\mu^n]$ where $\phi_\mu \in [\frac{\mu_{STP}}{f_\mu} : \mu_{STP} \times f_\mu]$;

$\Phi_\gamma \leftarrow [\phi_\gamma^0, \phi_\gamma^1, \phi_\gamma^2, \dots, \phi_\gamma^n]$ where $\phi_\gamma \in [\frac{\gamma_{STP}}{f_\gamma} : \gamma_{STP} \times f_\gamma]$;

$\Phi \leftarrow \Phi_\mu + \Phi_\gamma$;

Build Least-squares \mathbb{M} matrix;

$[t_{in}, \mathbf{F}_{in}] \leftarrow$ Global slosh forces time and force history;

while $t_{simu} < t_{end}$ **do**

 Advance time step (n);

$t_{simu} \leftarrow t_{in}^n$;

$\mathbf{F}_{Target} \leftarrow \mathbf{F}_{in}^n$;

 Update `SettGlob.inp` to limit simulation time to t_{simu} ;

 Define error vector ($\mathbb{E} = \emptyset$);

for $i = 1 : n(\Phi)$ **do**

 Update `SettMesh.inp.0` for fluid properties in Φ^i ;

 Execute ELEMENTAL[®] Simulation;

$F_{simu} \leftarrow$ ELEMENTAL[®] simulation Loads at $t = t_{simu}$;

 Append \mathbb{E} with $\frac{|F_{simu} - F_{Target}|}{\max |F_{Target}|}$

end

 LS Surface fitting providing $f(\phi)$ for discrete values of \mathbb{E} ;

$\Phi_{min} = \emptyset$;

 SDM to find local minimums for function $\min(f(\phi)) \rightarrow \phi_{min}^p$;

if $n(\Phi_{min}) = 0$ **then**

 SDM to find nearest intercept to $\phi = [\mu_{STP}, \gamma_{STP}]$ for the function

$f(\phi) = 0 \rightarrow \phi_{min}^p$;

end

 Update `SettMesh.inp.0` for fluid properties for $\min(f(\Phi_{min}))$;

 Execute ELEMENTAL[®] Simulation;

$F_{simu} \leftarrow$ ELEMENTAL[®] simulation Loads at $t = t_{simu}$;

$\epsilon_{min} \leftarrow \frac{|F_{simu} - F_{Target}|}{\max |F_{Target}|}$;

 Data and results write-out;

end

Appendix B

Ethics Application Form

ETHICS APPLICATION FORM

Please Note:

Any person planning to undertake research in the Faculty of Engineering and the Built Environment (EBE) at the University of Cape Town is required to complete this form **before** collecting or analysing data. The objective of submitting this application *prior* to embarking on research is to ensure that the highest ethical standards in research, conducted under the auspices of the EBE Faculty, are met. Please ensure that you have read, and understood the **EBE Ethics in Research Handbook** (available from the UCT EBE, Research Ethics website) prior to completing this application form: <http://www.ebe.uct.ac.za/ebe/research/ethics1>

APPLICANT'S DETAILS		
Name of principal researcher, student or external applicant	Michael Wright	
Department	Mechanical Engineering	
Preferred email address of applicant:	wrgmic010@myuct.ac.za	
If Student	Your Degree: e.g., MSc, PhD, etc.	PhD
	Credit Value of Research: e.g., 60/120/180/360 etc.	360
	Name of Supervisor (if supervised):	Prof. Arnaud Malan
If this is a research contract, indicate the source of funding/sponsorship		
Project Title	A Non-Linear Reduced Order Pressure Distribution Model for Vertical Slosh	

I hereby undertake to carry out my research in such a way that:

- there is no apparent legal objection to the nature or the method of research; and
- the research will not compromise staff or students or the other responsibilities of the University;
- the stated objective will be achieved, and the findings will have a high degree of validity;
- limitations and alternative interpretations will be considered;
- the findings could be subject to peer review and publicly available; and
- I will comply with the conventions of copyright and avoid any practice that would constitute plagiarism.

APPLICATION BY	Full name	Signature	Date
Principal Researcher/ Student/External applicant	Michael Wright	<i>MD Wright</i>	7/6/2021
SUPPORTED BY	Full name	Signature	Date
Supervisor (where applicable)	Arnaud Malan	<i>AMalan</i>	20/6/21

APPROVED BY	Full name	Signature	Date
HOD (or delegated nominee) Final authority for all applicants who have answered NO to all questions in Section 1; and for all Undergraduate research (Including Honours).			
Chair: Faculty EIR Committee For applicants other than undergraduate students who have answered YES to any of the questions in Section 1.	Prof. H. von Blottnitz	<i>H. von Blottnitz</i>	20/08/2021

Appendix C

Editor Declaration

Gemini Editing Services

(Sole proprietor: Adrienne Pretorius)
082-937-8283 (cell, b & WhatsApp)
e-mail: pretorii@mweb.co.za

96 Sandown Village
27 Harvey Road
PINETOWN
3610

15 March 2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN:

EDITING OF PhD (MECHANICAL ENGINEERING) DISSERTATION

PREPARED BY MICHAEL WRIGHT (MARCH 2022)

I, **Adrienne Mavis Pretorius**, a sole proprietor trading as **Gemini Editing Services**, hereby declare that I was asked by **MICHAEL WRIGHT**, a student of the University of Cape Town, to edit and proofread his PhD (Mechanical Engineering) dissertation as a third-party editor.

I am a professional editor with 35 years' experience in the field, and have the necessary qualifications and experience to carry out these tasks.

I confirm that in acting as a third-party editor for the dissertation submitted by the abovenamed student, **MICHAEL WRIGHT**, I have complied with all professional requirements for editorial help for postgraduate research theses/dissertations. My work with regard to this thesis was confined to the following areas:

- * Checking of the various elements of the tables of contents
- * Formatting of the document
- * Checking of spelling and punctuation
- * Ensuring that the thesis/dissertation follows the conventions of grammar, spelling and syntax in written UK/South African English
- * Shortening long sentences and editing long paragraphs to ensure easy reading and comprehension of the content
- * Elimination of unnecessary repetition
- * Checking tables and diagrams for clarity, grammar, spelling and punctuation of any text relating to the tables and diagrams
- * Checking correct presentation of references in the applicable referencing convention, as well as full and accurate citation, and
- * Ensuring consistency of page numbers, headers and footers.

I have advised the student that this completed form **must** accompany his dissertation when he submits it for examination, and that **this declaration will be made available to the examiners**. I have further advised **MICHAEL WRIGHT** to keep a copy for his records.

Yours faithfully

(Mrs) Adrienne Pretorius

(BA (*cum laude*)) (UNISA)

(Full Member of the Professional Editors' Group (PEG))

Signature: _____

Signature: (See scanned image above.) Date: 15 March 2022

[Please note that I suffer from severe rheumatoid arthritis and am no longer able to sign individual documents. I therefore have to insert a scan.]